

CATALISI

Catalysation of institutional transformations
of Higher Education Institutions through
the adoption of acceleration services

D6.1 DATA AND QUALITY MANAGEMENT PLAN 31/12/2025

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01

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D6.1

DATA AND QUALITY MANAGEMENT PLAN

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Abstract	This deliverable describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the CATALISI project. Moreover, it provides information about how to manage personal data according to GDPR Regulation. Finally, it set the internal rule to guarantee a quality management. This deliverable was updated in December 2025 to provide complete information about the data that was collected and processed during the project implementation.
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The current deliverable, entitled 'Data and Quality Management Plan' (DQMP), was developed within the framework of the CATALISI project which is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N. 101094917.

This deliverable describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the project. As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable (FAIR), the Data Management Plan (DMP) provides a summary of the main elements that should be considered in the definition of the data management policy to be used by the project partners throughout the project activities. The DMP provides indications about the management of all the data generated during the project activities, including how data will be collected, managed, stored and made available during the project and how they will be shared after the project end.

In addition, the deliverable describes data processing procedures used by the CATALISI consortium, applicable legislation as well as includes informed consent template that will be used during project implementation. The information contained in this document will represent a key point of reference for all project activities that will involve humans, such as the participants in all project events (workshops, trainings, webinars, meetings, etc.), and/or in interviews/surveys (online and in person) run by the project. The document contains also information about compliance with EU and national data protection rules under GDPR, of each CATALISI Beneficiary.

Finally, the deliverable is a collection of instructions and processes regarding the project management and administration to set up a quality system for the CATALISI project, which is followed by all project partners.

This deliverable was updated in December 2025 to provide complete information about the data that was collected and processed during the project implementation. In specific:

- section 2.3 'Data collected in CATALISI Tasks' was updated with final information about the data that was processed in each Task where such processing was needed and/or required;
- Appendix 3 was added to provide more detailed information about datasets used for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities;
- Section 2.4 'Data shared with third parties' was added to provide information about data that was shared with CATALISI sister projects and through joint communication, dissemination and exploitation activities (addressing the following comment from the interim review meeting: *'plan the revision of the respective Data Management Plans to reflect possible agreements related to aspects as: joint acceleration services developments, sharing of activities and documents, external communication material or others of relevance'*). To this end, Appendix 4 and Appendix 5 were added to showcase the formal agreements that were signed with sister projects.

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TABLE OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
T	Task
WP	Work-Package
PC	Project Coordinator
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
EY	Ernst & Young
F6S	F6s Network Ireland Limited
ENoLL	European Network Of Living Labs
KTU	Kauno Technologijos Universitetas
UJI	Universitat Jaume I De Castellon
LUISS	Luiss Libera Universita Internazionale Degli Studi Sociali Guido Carli
UG	Uniwersytet Gdanski
UCC	University College Cork - National University Of Ireland, Cork
AUTH	Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis
VUMC	Stichting Vum
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digita Object Identification
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
DPO	Data Protection Officer
IP	Intellectual Property

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND AND AIM

Institutional transformation is a key strategy to address the challenges of Research and Innovation (R&I) and to govern and drive the transformations affecting science and innovation. Institutional changes of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) enables to better align R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society (European Commission, 2020). Research and Innovation topics have been in fact geared towards establishing institutional changes in education institutes opening them up to closer cooperation with citizens and civil society.

With these premises in mind, the CATALISI project is overall aimed at contributing to the EC objective of spreading and embedding Research & Innovation in the European Research Area through the facilitation and acceleration of institutional transformations of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in seven research organisations. The overall objective of the project is to assist HEIs to successfully implement a strategy and individual pathway for institutional transformation benefitting of acceleration services.

For each research organisation, institutional transformations will be incorporated in a strategy and individual pathway that will provide the basis for medium and long terms sustainable institutional change towards R&I. In fact, Institutional transformation is expected to have meaningful impact within the institution concerned and intended to last beyond the lifetime of project funding (European Commission, 2020). In CATALISI, transformational pathways will set the ground and "pave the way" towards long-term changes.

To achieve institutional transformation, HEIs will benefit from seven targeted and innovative acceleration services: Living Labs, Design lab for transformational pathway; Counselling; Reinforce Human Capital; Predictive study on skills anticipation; Marketplace; Community of practice (CoP). Also, HEIs are committed to introduce and implement new reforms in their structures intervening on specific domains and intervention areas. The domains identified in CATALISI are: Human Capital, Research Modus Operandi and Finance, which respectively composed by different intervention areas, that indicate the content of specific institutional transformations that can be deemed necessary by each HEIs.

The project involves 11 partners, of which 7 are the HEIs, who will pursue institutional transformations (so-called "implementers") while 4 (the so-called "facilitators") will assist the HEIs to implement a strategy and individual pathway for institutional transformation.

1.2 AIM AND STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The current Deliverable '**Data and Quality Management Plan**' (DQMP), is developed within the framework of the CATALISI project which is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094917.

The Deliverable describes the processes for an effective coordination of the project and for the data management plan, it is therefore structured around three main themes:

- ✓ DATA MANAGEMENT (chapter 2)
- ✓ ETHICS AND PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION (chapter 3)
- ✓ QUALITY MANAGEMENT (chapter 4)

The Chapter **2** describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the CATALISI consortium. It will define the main elements to be used by the project partners during the project to make research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR). As part of this, this chapter constitutes the project **Data Management Plan (DMP)** and provides indications about the management of all data generated during the project activities, including how data will be collected, managed, stored and made available during the project and how they will be shared after the project ends.

The Chapter **3** describes the application of the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to guarantee a coherent approach towards data protection and privacy issues during CATALISI activities implementation, despite the various differences across the EU Member States legal frameworks. To confirm compliance with EU and national data protection rules under GDPR, each CATALISI Beneficiary signed a '**Declaration on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection**' (Appendix 1); when a Beneficiary was required to appoint a Data Protection Officers (DPO), his/her contact details are reported in the document (Appendix 2).

The Chapter **4** constitutes the project **Quality Management Plan** and provides an overview of the management structure, describes the responsibilities of the partners, defines the procedures for ensuring the quality of project deliverables. It describes also how to communicate within the consortium as well as presents procedures for monitoring and reporting activities.

The 'Data and Quality Management Plan' (DQMP) is a living document and it was updated during project implementation according to project's needs. Evidence of these changes will be provided in the periodic evaluation/assessment of the project (period reports).

2 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

2.1 Data Management in CATALISI – overview

2.1.1 Objectives and structure of the Data Management Plan

Chapter 2 of this deliverable aims to describe the overall data management process within CATALISI, in particular which data are generated and how they will be collected, managed, processed, stored and made available during the life of the project, as well as how they will be preserved and shared beyond. This is an important aspect of any research project and therefore it is essential to plan an effective data management since the early stages.

CATALISI involves the collaboration of 11 beneficiaries and a moderate amount of data will be generated in various activities. All data collected and generated during the project will be managed according to the FAIR principles in order to be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.

A good Data Management Plan (DMP) can reduce the risk of data loss or other threats that could make the data unreadable or unusable, and can guarantee their accessibility and preservation in the long term. Good data management also increases the knowledge discovery and innovation, as the data are re-used by the community after their publication process¹.

The management of data generated during the project will aim to ensure open access, as stated in the Article 29.3 of the Grant Agreement, taking into account the principle of "*as open as possible, as closed as necessary*", in order to ensure the adoption of appropriate measures to preserve project results that can be further exploited in the future. Thus, the project will pursue a balance between openness and protection of information, commercialisation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, security, etc. If project partners need to keep certain parts of their data closed, this choice will be explicitly indicated in this DMP.

The CATALISI Data Management Plan (DMP) specifically:

- provides an overview of the data that will be collected and processed in each Task (see § 2.3), where data management is required;
- describes (see § 2.4) where and how the data generated by the project activities will be stored (information about the IT infrastructure used will be also provided);
- details how data will be documented to ensure that new members of the CATALISI team and/or any possible (secondary) users are able to understand and reuse the data (see § 2.5);
- describes the level of data confidentiality and the responsibility of the individual organizations, within CATALISI, involved in the data collection processes (see § 2.6);
- describes how the data will be shared (see § 2.7) and where they will be deposited for preserving all the material produced (see § 2.8);

¹ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

2.1.2 Data management during CATALISI lifetime

APRE, as project coordinator, will be responsible for coordinating the data management with the active support of WP Leaders and Task Leaders. The partner responsible for the generation of data in the task in question will also be responsible for the securing of the data for release via open access repositories when these are open.

During the progress of the project implementation and when the final results are achieved, if needed, the content of the DMP will be enriched. Therefore, this deliverable was updated in December 2025. Evidence of the updates will be provided in the reporting documents.

2.1.3 Long term data management

Having in mind the data management purposes, and that the data generated will be useful, findable and reusable over the long-term for the end-users, the long-term storage of CATALISI data will be guaranteed through a dedicated [ZENODO CATALISI Community](#), which will also avoid the risk of data loss.

The data stored on ZENODO will automatically have a persistent identifier, namely a DOI, to datasets to allow easy citation and discoverability. ZENODO offers free data archiving up to 50 GB per dataset, which is sufficient, given the expected data volume in the CATALISI project.

2.2 Data Collection

2.2.1 Data information

During the CATALISI project, various types of data will be collected and documented.

This section describes the data that will be collected in each Task (if applicable), as indicated by the Task Leaders.

Type of Data

In research projects, usually different types of data (observational, experimental, simulation, derived or compiled, reference or canonical and event related) may be collected and documented. Since CATALISI is a Coordination and Support Action, no experimental data will be collected. However, the following categories of data will be collected:

- ✓ **Technical Data:** recorded information related to technical activities (e.g. analysis of existing practices, development of new solutions, mapping of relevant initiatives/projects, etc.). The collection may require surveys, interviews, instruments to record, transformation of existing datasets to create new data, etc.
- ✓ **Stakeholders Data:** such as Contact Details or any other (personal) data of CATALISI stakeholders. The collection may involve registration forms to events, newsletter subscription, website, etc. The handling of those data will take into account GDPR.

It is worth to point out that administrative/financial data (data strictly related to the management of the project, e.g. meeting minutes, collection of information about partners' expenditures, etc.) is not included in the technical data definition, and in CATALISI project it will be considered 'other data'. Moreover, the identified categories can occasionally overlap, and data can belong to more than one category depending on the specificities of the data itself.

Format of the data and estimated size

Collected data come in various formats: electronic text, spreadsheets, multimedia, models, software languages, etc. For the concerned Task, it will be described the format of the data produced, with the ultimate goal to facilitate the accessibility and interoperability of the data, giving preferences to open and standard formats. In this deliverable, a first estimation of the size of the data collected in each Task will also be provided. This information was updated in the final version of CATALISI DMP according to the actual size of data collected.

2.2.2 Organization of data collected

The data collected within CATALISI will be organized taking into consideration the following aspects, as far as applicable.

Version Control

To overcome the challenge of managing and tracking research materials during the course of a project, especially in collaborative projects, data will be organized to keep track of different versions of the datasets, through the application of a version control system. A version control system (or revision control system) is a system that tracks incremental versions (or revisions) of files and, in some cases, directories over time (such as v0.1, v0.2 etc.). Improving the ability to consistently track and retrieve each version of a file can lead to more

efficient collaboration and increased accuracy of research results. Through the version control system, the risk of losing information after modifications is minimized.

Versioning is important for long term-research data management where metadata and/or files are updated over time.

Naming conventions used

With the overall aim to make the data accessible (and ultimately foster reproducible research), CATALISI datasets will be carefully named by choosing file names that are informative and useful for both humans and machines. Name should be meaningful to allow others to better understand what the file contains and how it should be used. Following, there are some suggestions about the naming conventions within CATALISI:

Choose machine readable names

Use deliberate delimits. Common approach is using "_" and "-" to delimit units of metadata in the file names. A general rule could be to use "-" to separate words you want to glob together and "_" to separate different information within a file name. Don't use spaces, punctuation, capital letters or special characters (Using \$, @, %, #, &, *, (,), !, etc. may have meanings in programming languages).

Choose human readable names

Choose names that explain the content. The more meaningful the name, the more useful it is for human users. The more metadata you store in the name, the less you need to explain elsewhere. Choose short names.

An example can be: university_survey_10022024

2.3 Data collected in CATALISI Tasks

The first version of the CATALISI DMP mapped 10 datasets whose key details are summarized in the Table 1.

TABLE 1 SUMMARY CATALISI DATASETS

DATASET NAME	PARTNER	SOURCE	SIZE	TASK	ACCESSIBILITY
Stakeholder_DB	ENoLL	Existing & Generated	<100K B	T1.1	Restricted to consortium
LearningHUB_DB	EY/F6S	Existing.	<100K B	T2.1	Restricted to consortium
MML_Workshops_DB	APRE	Existing & Generated	5GB	T2.3	Restricted to consortium

Predictive_study_DB	EY	Existing & Generated	<100KB	T3.3	Restricted to consortium
Evaluation_Impact_Assessment Framework_DB	UCC	Generated	<100KB	T4.1	Restricted to consortium
Monitoring_DB	UCC	Generated	<100KB	T4.2	Restricted to consortium
Capacity_Impact_Assessment	UCC	Generated	<100KB	T4.3	Restricted to consortium members.
Dissemination_DB	F6S/APRE	Existing & Generated	<2GB	T5.2	Restricted to consortium members.
Management_DB	APRE	Existing & Generated	<100KB	T6.1	Restricted to consortium members.
CoP_Database	APRE	Existing & Generated	2GB	T6.3	Restricted to consortium members.

In the framework of an update of the CATALISI DMP (December 2025), all Task Leaders were requested to provide final information about the data that was collected and processed during the project implementation in their respective tasks.

The following tables present the final data that was collected and processed in CATALISI tasks. As CATALISI is a Coordination and Support Action, no research data in the strict sense was produced. However, the project collected the following data categories:

- **Technical data:** information generated through operational activities (e.g., analysis of existing practices, descriptions of methodologies/practices/tools used, mapping of relevant initiatives/projects/stakeholders). Collection methods may include surveys, interviews, recording tools or transformation of existing datasets.
- **Stakeholder data:** contact details and other personal information related to CATALISI stakeholders, gathered through event/webinar/workshop registrations, newsletter subscriptions, website access, etc.
- **Financial/administrative data:** strictly related to the management of the project (e.g., meeting minutes, partner expenditure reporting).

Task 1.1 Setting-up CATALISI Acting Living Labs

Data description	Data generated during the setup of the Acting Living Labs with the HEIs was primarily collected through the stakeholder mapping exercises, in which the seven HEIs identified the stakeholders relevant to their institutional transformation journeys and to the establishment of their Acting Living Labs. In addition, the setup phase provided the HEIs with a training session on Living Lab basics and methodological tools to help them better understand and apply the Living Lab methodology
Data collector	ENoLL
Data source/origin	Stakeholder-mapping workshops; Living Lab training session (recording + materials)
Purpose of data collection	To support the establishment of the Acting Living Labs, ensure that HEIs identified all relevant stakeholders for their institutional transformation processes, and provide methodological grounding through training. The data was used to inform the design of the LL activities, guide engagement strategies, and ensure alignment with the Living Lab methodology.
Type of data collected	Stakeholders data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT / .PPTX (training slides) • MP4 (training recording)
Size of data	Approx. 50–150 MB
Open availability of produced data	Closed – available only for consortium members and the EC, if requested
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI shared folder (restricted access) • ENoLL's server

Task 1.2 Exploration Phase of the Acting Living Labs

Data description	Data was generated during the first round of Exploration Workshops conducted by each HEI to analyse their institutional context, stakeholder needs, and the challenges and barriers to transformation. The data includes qualitative insights produced from workshop discussions, completed templates, facilitation notes, context analyses, and stakeholder-input summaries. In addition, registrants lists for the workshops were collected, containing participant names, affiliations, and contact details used to organise and document stakeholder engagement activities.
Data collector	HEIs (data generation and collection), ENoLL (methodological guidance and consolidation)
Data source/origin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploration Workshops (Round 1) • Workshop templates and reports • Registrants lists for the workshops

Purpose of data collection	To understand each HEI's local ecosystem, identify stakeholder needs and barriers, and generate evidence to support the co-design of transformation actions. The registrants lists enabled correct documentation of stakeholder engagement, tracking participation, and reporting on LL activities. All collected data informed the development and refinement of Action Plans.
Type of data collected	Stakeholders data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOC / .DOCX (workshop reports) • Word (registrants lists) • .PPT / .PPTX (workshop presentations) • Photo formats (.JPEG, .PNG) — workshop documentation
Size of data	Approx. 30–100 MB per HEI
Open availability of produced data	Classified – available only to the partner that gathered the data and the EC, if requested (Due to the inclusion of personal data in registrants lists and sensitive stakeholder contributions.)
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI shared folder (restricted access) • Partners' internal servers(ENoLL and participating H EIs)

Task 1.3 Co-design Phase of the Acting Living Labs

Data description	<p>Data was generated during the second round of Co-design Workshops, where each HEI collaboratively developed and refined its institutional transformation Action Plan. Outputs include co-creation notes, ideation results, prioritised actions, defined stakeholder roles, timelines, and expected impacts, along with filled co-design templates and facilitation notes.</p> <p>In addition, a validation survey was developed and completed by stakeholders to verify the relevance, feasibility, and completeness of the drafted Action Plans. The survey generated structured quantitative and qualitative feedback.</p> <p>Registrants lists were also collected, containing participant names, affiliations, and contact details, documenting stakeholder involvement in the co-design process.</p>
Data collector	HEIs (workshop data, registrants lists) ENoLL (methodological guidance, consolidation of inputs and survey insights)
Data source/origin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-design templates and worksheets • Facilitator notes and group outputs • Draft Action Plans • Action Plan Validation Survey (response) • Registrants lists

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-design Workshops (Round 2)
Purpose of data collection	To co-create and structure each HEI's Action Plan using participatory methods, ensuring alignment with stakeholder needs and institutional priorities. The validation survey was used to confirm the robustness, clarity, and stakeholder acceptance of the drafted Action Plans before finalisation. Registrants lists were collected to document participation and engagement for reporting and methodological tracking.
Type of data collected	Stakeholders data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOC / .DOCX (co-design notes, Action Plan drafts) • XLS / .XLSX (registrants lists, , exported survey data) • CSV (survey response exports, • PPT / .PPTX (workshop and survey presentation material) • PDF survey reports • Photo formats (.JPEG, .PNG) — workshop documentation
Size of data	Approx. 50–150 MB per HEI
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classified – available only to the partner that gathered the data and the EC, if requested
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI shared folder (restricted access) • Partners' internal servers (ENoLL + individual HEIs)

T1.4 Implementation Phase

T1.5 Evaluation Phase

Data description	<p>Data was generated through the implementation of the Action Plans and the evaluation of the Acting Living Labs. For T1.4, HEIs documented implemented actions, progress, and evidence of activities, and collected stakeholder feedback during implementation. Three training webinars on the Living Lab methodology produced recordings, presentation materials, and registrants lists.</p> <p>For T1.5, two surveys were carried out: one assessing the first phase of Action Plan implementation, and one evaluating the application of the Living Lab methodology and the implementation progress (completed by partners only). HEIs also provided concise reflections on achievements, barriers, and lessons learned.</p> <p>Registrants lists were collected for all relevant workshops and webinars.</p>
Data collector	HEIs (implementation data, stakeholder feedback, survey responses, registrants lists)

	ENoLL (training materials, consolidation of survey results) EY (for the jointly organised webinars)
Data source/origin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation documentation and activity outputs • Stakeholder feedback collected by HEIs • Training webinars (slides, recordings, registrants lists) • Survey on Action Plan implementation (Survey 1) • Survey on LL methodology and implementation progress (Survey 2 – internal)
Purpose of data collection	To track, document, and evaluate the implementation of the Action Plans, assess the use of the Living Lab methodology, identify challenges and achievements, and support capacity building through training.
Type of data collected	Stakeholders data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .XLS / .XLSX (registrants lists) • .CSV (survey response exports) • .PPT / .PPTX (training slides) • .MP4 (webinar recordings)
Size of data	Approx. 150–300 MB across all HEIs
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classified – available only to partners and the EC, if requested • Open for webinars and trainings
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI website • CATALISI Zenodo Community • CATALISI shared folder • Partners' servers

Task 2.1 Setting up the Learning Hub

Data description	Data generated from the development and operation of the CATALISI Learning Hub, including the design and delivery of training program for HEIs, participant registrations, feedback from webinars, and records of knowledge-sharing activities. The Learning Hub provides access to training, webinars, and resources for institutional transformation
Data collector	EY
Data source/origin	Needs analysis, good practices identified in WP1, participant registrations, webinar attendance, records, and content uploaded to the Learning Hub platform.
Purpose of data collection	To support and facilitate access to training for HEIs, monitor participation and engagement, and continuously improve the training program and knowledge-sharing activities
Type of data collected	<p>Technical data (training content, webinar recordings)</p> <p>Stakeholders data (participant names, roles, affiliations, emails)</p> <p>Administrative data (participation records)</p>

Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC / .DOCX • .XLS / .XLSX • .PPT / .PPTX • .CSV • .PDF • .MP4 • .JPEG/.PNG
Size of data	80 MB
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closed – available only for consortium members and the EC, if requested
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI website • CATALISI shared folder

Task 2.2 Development of the knowledge sharing methodology

Data description	Prior perspectives, knowledge and experience about the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Methodology amongst consortium partners and preliminary overview of topics considered relevant.
Data collector	APRE
Data source/origin	<p>Online short survey sent by APRE in May 2023 (M5) to each HEI in CATALISI to assess the state of the art of CATALISI Implementing partners on the knowledge regarding MML activities within their respective host organisation.</p> <p>Pre-existing data such as mapping of projects which have utilised MML methodology, such as H2020BIOVOICES (G.A. n. 774331) and H2020 TIMES4SC (G.A. n. 101006201), other relevant EU-funded projects e.g. MARINA H2020 project (G.A. ID: 710566, Grace H2020 project (G.A. 824521, SISCODE H2020 project (G.A. 788217).</p>
Purpose of data collection	Descriptions of the state of the art of The Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Methodology in CATALISI in the context of D.2.1.
Type of data collected	Technical data
Data format	.XLS / .XLSX
Size of data	50 MB
Open availability of produced data	Closed (available only for consortium members and the EC, if requested),
Data accessibility	APRE's server

Task 2.3 Multi level knowledge transfer among the implementers

Data description	Name, surname, role, affiliation of presenters (both within the HEIs and external stakeholders) that took part in the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Events in each of the
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	<p>CATALISI Higher Education Institutions organised in the context of T.2.3.</p> <p>Number and role of participants that attended the MML events.</p> <p>Overall assessment by CATALISI HEIs (analysis of MML effectiveness) and by participants.</p> <p>Photos and presentation of the MML events by CATALISI HEIs.</p> <p>Agendas of the events.</p>
Data collector	APRE / CATALISI HEIs in charge of the events' organization
Data source/origin	Stakeholder mapping and event participants. Reporting template. Workshop feedback survey to participants.
Purpose of data collection	Organisation, planning and reporting on the MML events organised in the context of T.2.3 and facilitated by APRE.
Type of data collected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical data • Stakeholders data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC / .DOCX • .XLS / .XLSX • .PPT / .PPTX • .PDF • Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
Size of data	
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closed (available only for consortium members and the EC, if requested); • Classified (available only to the partner that gathered the data and the EC, if requested), • Open (publicly available)
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI website, • CATALISI Zenodo Community, • CATALISI shared folder (WP2), • Partner's server

Task 2.4 Exchange the knowledge through Twinning schemes

Data description	<p>Evidence-based matchmaking framework, aligning the support needs of less experienced institutions with the demonstrated expertise of potential hosting HEIs.</p> <p>Name, surname, role, affiliation of presenters (both within the HEIs and external stakeholders) that took part in the Twinning exchanges in each of the CATALISI Higher Education Institutions organised in the context of T.2.4.</p> <p>Number and role of participants that attended the Twinning exchanges.</p> <p>Overall assessment by CATALISI HEIs (analysis of Twinning effectiveness).</p> <p>Photos and PPT presentation used during the Twinning events by CATALISI HEIs.</p>
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	Agendas of the events.
Data collector	APRE / CATALISI HEIs in charge of the events' organization
Data source/origin	Short internal survey to CATALISI HEIs by APRE. Stakeholder mapping and event participants. Reporting template.
Purpose of data collection	Organisation, planning and reporting on the Twinning events organised in the context of T.2.4 and facilitated by APRE.
Type of data collected	Technical data Stakeholders data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC / .DOCX • .XLS / .XLSX • .PPT / .PPTX • .PDF • Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
Size of data	
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classified (available only to the partner that gathered the data and the EC, if requested), • Closed (available only for consortium members and the EC, if requested), • Open (publicly available)
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI website, • CATALISI Zenodo Community, • CATALISI shared folder (WP2), • Partner's server

Task 3.1 Coordination and definition of Counselling service

Data description	Data generated from the design, implementation, and monitoring of coaching and mentoring services for HEIs, including participant information, needs assessments, and records of service usage.
Data collector	EY
Data source/origin	Surveys, interviews, needs assessments, and records from coaching/mentoring sessions with HEIs.
Purpose of data collection	To design, implement, and monitor tailored coaching and mentoring services supporting institutional transformation in HEIs.
Type of data collected	Technical data Stakeholders data Administrative data (participation records)
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC / .DOCX • .XLS / .XLSX • .PPT / .PPTX • .CSV • .PDF

Size of data	MB
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closed (available only for consortium members and the EC, if requested)
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI shared folder • EY server

Task 3.2 Design Lab for Transformational Pathway: Strategy and Agenda Setting

Data description	Data from the development and tailoring of transformational pathways for HEIs, including action plans, roadmaps, workshop outputs and feedback from stakeholders.
Data collector	EY
Data source/origin	Workshops, co-creation sessions, feedback forms, and strategic planning documents developed with HEIs and stakeholders.
Purpose of data collection	To develop, refine, and monitor institutional transformation pathways and agendas for HEIs.
Type of data collected	Technical data Stakeholders data (names, roles, affiliations, emails) Administrative data (participation records, feedback)
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC / .DOCX • .XLS / .XLSX • .PPT / .PPTX • .CSV • .PDF
Size of data	MB
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open (publicly available) - for action plans and roadmaps • Closed (available only for consortium members and the EC, if requested) – for the remaining data
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI website • CATALISI Zenodo Community • CATALISI shared folder • EY server

Task 3.3 Predictive Study

Data description	Data generated from the predictive study on future skills and professions, including survey results, expert workshop outputs, chatbot investigations, and AI-based analyses.
Data collector	EY
Data source/origin	Interviews with researchers and business representatives, surveys, large-scale chatbot investigations, public data sources, literature review, and AI analysis outputs.

Purpose of data collection	To forecast future skills and labor market needs, supporting HEIs in planning training and development actions.
Type of data collected	Technical data Stakeholders data (names, roles, affiliations, emails) Survey Data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC / .DOCX • .XLS / .XLSX • .PPT / .PPTX • .CSV • .PDF
Size of data	MB
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open (publicly available) • Closed (available only for consortium members and the EC, if requested) – for stakeholder data
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI website • CATALISI Zenodo Community • CATALISI shared folder • Partner's server

Task 3.4 Market Place: Support to Sustainable funding

Data description	Information regarding the (acceleration) services provided by the project partners, incl. type of service, background, description and contacts. Contacts provided by the partners are limited to: name, surname, position and affiliation to the partner entity.
Data collector	F6S
Data source/origin	Data was collected via survey distributed and filled in by the project partners.
Purpose of data collection	The collected data was displayed on the project website in the CATALYST Hub (former Marketplace, publicly available) for the purpose of showcasing and promoting further usage of the CATALISI services provided by the partners.
Type of data collected	Technical data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC / .DOCX
Size of data	2MB
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open (publicly available)
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI website • F6S server

Task 4.2 Roadmap implementation monitoring and data collection

Data description	Formative bilateral meetings between UCC and implementing partners. Meeting conducted in Teams
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	meetings. Notes taken down on word doc. This data falls also under task 4.3.
Data collector	UCC
Data source/origin	Bilateral meetings (also task 4.3, already compiled).
Purpose of data collection	Data fed into the final evaluation report
Type of data collected	Technical data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC /.DOCX • Dashboard
Size of data	Less than 5 MBs
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classified: final internal report based on bilateral notes • Closed: individual bilateral meeting notes
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI shared folder • UCC server

Data description	KPIs collected through formative activities conducted with implementing partners (bilaterals). This data set also falls under task 4.4
Data collector	UCC
Data source/origin	Bilateral meetings (also task 4.4, already compiled).
Purpose of data collection	Data fed into the final evaluation report
Type of data collected	Technical data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excel
Size of data	Less than 5 MBs
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closed: implementers KPIs are present on final 4.2 deliverable.
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI shared folder • UCC server

Task 4.3 Capacity-building for impact assessment

Data description	Summative self-assessment survey conducted in June 2025. Contains answers regarding WP4 related work and basic info on responders. Data in form format, excel sheets and word docs.
Data collector	UCC
Data source/origin	Final self-assessment summative survey, Microsoft forms
Purpose of data collection	Data fed into the final evaluation report
Type of data collected	Technical data Stakeholder data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC /.DOCX • Microsoft Form • Excel
Size of data	Less than 5 MBs

Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Classified: final internal report and results from self-assessment survey.
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UCC's server

Data description	Workshop conducted in AUTH GA in January 2025. Conducted on poster with sticky notes, converted to Miro board. Results contained in word docs. Some photos taken during workshop and of posters, answers for note-taking purposes.
Data collector	UCC
Data source/origin	Workshop at GA in AUTH, January 2025.
Purpose of data collection	Data fed into the final evaluation report
Type of data collected	Technical data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> .DOC /.DOCX Photos (AUTH workshop) Posters and sticky notes (AUTH workshop) Miro boards (AUTH workshop)
Size of data	Less than 5 MBs for docs and miro boards More than 5 MBs for photos
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Classified: Posters and sticky notes. Miro boards. Closed: Report from workshop at AUTH GA. Photos from workshop.
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CATALISI shared folder Partner's server

Data description	Formative bilateral meetings between UCC and implementing partners. Meeting conducted in Teams meetings. Notes taken down on word doc. This data falls also under task 4.2.
Data collector	UCC
Data source/origin	Bilateral meetings (also task 4.2, already compiled).
Purpose of data collection	Data fed into the final evaluation report
Type of data collected	Technical data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> .DOC /.DOCX
Size of data	Less than 5 MBs
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Classified: final internal report based on bilateral notes Closed: individual bilateral meeting notes
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CATALISI shared folder UCC server

Task 4.4 Development of monitoring and impact assessment toolkits

Data description	KPIs collected through formative activities conducted with implementing partners (bilaterals). This data set also falls under task 4.2
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Data collector	UCC
Data source/origin	Bilateral meetings (also task 4.2, already compiled).
Purpose of data collection	Data fed into the final evaluation report
Type of data collected	Technical data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excel • Dashboard
Size of data	Less than 5 MBs
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closed: implementers KPIs are present on final 4.2 deliverable.
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI shared folder • UCC server

Task 4.5 Policy Recommendations

Data description	Data generated from the development of policy recommendations for universities, alliances, and policymakers at local, national, and European levels. This includes analysis of project evaluation and assessment results, feedback from co-creation events, and stakeholder consultations. Data covers technical findings, participant information, and administrative records related to the policy recommendation process.
Data collector	EY
Data source/origin	Evaluation and impact assessment data (from WP4, led by UCC with EY as contributor); feedback from co-creation events; stakeholder consultations, stakeholder interviews; literature review, survey and workshop results.
Purpose of data collection	To provide strategic information and guidance on structural and institutional changes needed to maximize research value and impact in Europe; to inform policy at multiple levels based on project evidence and stakeholder input.
Type of data collected	Technical data (evaluation results, policy drafts) Stakeholders data (names, roles, affiliations, emails) Administrative data (records of consultation events, feedback forms)
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC / .DOCX • .XLS / .XLSX • .PPT / .PPTX • .CSV • .PDF
Size of data	70 MB
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open (publicly available) • Closed (available only for consortium members and the EC, if requested) – for stakeholder data

Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI website • CATALISI Zenodo Community • CATALISI shared folder • Partner's server
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Task ask 4.6 Creation of evaluation mechanisms to be super visioned by an external acceleration board

Data description	Name, surname, email, role, affiliation of External acceleration board members; Bank account details of the EAB members. EAB evaluation feedback. Agenda and presentations of the meetings with EAB members.
Data collector	APRE
Data source/origin	Stakeholder mapping, external sources, assessment guidelines.
Purpose of data collection	External experts to evaluate the transformational pathways of the implementers pursuing institutional transformation within T.4.6.
Type of data collected	Technical data Stakeholders data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC / .DOCX • .PDF
Size of data	
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classified (available only to the partner that gathered the data and the EC, if requested), • Closed (available only for consortium members and the EC, if requested),
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI shared folder • APRE server

Task 5.1 Dissemination & Communication strategy

Task 5.2 Communication & Awareness raising activities

Task 5.3 Dissemination activities

Data description	<p>Within the communication and dissemination activities data was collected for the organization, promotion and implementation of events (online and on-site). The partners organizing the events collected data regarding the participants registration and attendance for dissemination and reporting purposes. Additional data was collected from the project partners in order to develop dissemination materials, e.g. leaflets, booklets, flyers, etc. When personal data was collected, it was limited to name, surname, position and affiliation to the partner entity (as speaker in a webinar, representative of the partner or contact point for further</p>
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	information, etc.). No personal emails were collected or displayed but organizational ones. Finally, photos and videos or recordings of events were done also for dissemination purposes. All participants were informed and consent forms were signed for this purpose.
Data collector	F6S and partners organizing events
Data source/origin	For this purpose, different channels were used to obtain the data, including: email exchange (e.g. with speakers, sister and synergy projects to obtain the information needed for agenda and presentations preparation and promotion, etc.); registration platforms (e.g. Zoom, Teams – for registration and attendance monitoring of the participants in webinars); participants list (for physical events); recordings of webinars (published on the project website for training purposes), etc.
Purpose of data collection	The data collected was used with different purpose, incl.: dissemination (e.g. promotion of events and project results through dissemination materials); reporting (e.g. monitoring attendance of the events).
Type of data collected	Technical data Stakeholders data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC / .DOCX • .XLS / .XLSX • .PPT / .PPTX • .PDF • Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG) • Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)
Size of data	
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classified (available only to the partner that gathered the data and the EC, if requested) – e.g. registration forms, consent forms, etc. • Closed (available only for consortium members and the EC, if requested) – e.g. list with attendees, photos, videos, etc. • Open (publicly available) – selected photos, videos, promotional materials like flyers, booklets, etc.
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI website • CATALISI Zenodo Community • CATALISI shared folder

More detailed information about collection of the datasets used for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities is available in Appendix 3.

Task 5.4 Exploitation activities and preparation

Data description	Data was generated during the Exploitation Workshops and followup activities (e.g. survey) conducted with all partners to analyse their insti
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	tutional context and the exploitation intentions. The data includes qualitative insights produced from workshop discussions, completed templates and survey, facilitation notes. Similarly, more detailed exploitation intentions and plans data was collected within the Horizon Booster sessions with 3 partners owning selected KERs (APRE, EY and ENoLL).
Data collector	F6S
Data source/origin	Data generated during the exploitation task with the project partners was primarily collected through the KER-identification exercises, in which the partners shared their interest and intentions towards the exploitation of the project results after its end. In addition, a series of online workshops with the goal to discuss the exploitation potential were conducted, as well as a survey shared with and filled in by the project partners. The selected 3 KERs were further developed within the Horizon Booster support sessions.
Purpose of data collection	The working files, such as survey results and minutes from the workshops and exercise are internal to the consortium and will remain closed to the project partners, while the findings were incorporated in D5.2 Final Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Sustainability Plan (a public deliverable available on the project website). The filled in templates supporting the exploitation efforts within the Horizon Booster programme (e.g. exploitation roadmap, use options, lean canvas, etc.) for the 3 selected KERs (owned by APRE, EY and ENoLL), are also joined to the final D5.2, thus publicly available.
Type of data collected	Technical data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC / .DOCX • .XLS / .XLSX • .PPT / .PPTX
Size of data	Approx. 50–300 MB
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closed (available only for consortium members and the EC, if requested) • Open (publicly available within published deliverable)
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI website (within published deliverable) • CATALISI shared folder

Task 6.1 Project Management

Data description	Minutes of monthly, annual and coordination meetings with partners; Recording of Monthly Meetings; Calendar events planning
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	and reporting; Agendas and powerpoints of the meetings; Partner expenditure reporting and technical reporting
Data collector	APRE
Data source/origin	recording tools
Purpose of data collection	<i>Short explanation of how the data was used in the project/for what purpose</i>
Type of data collected	Technical data Stakeholders data Financial/administrative data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC / .DOCX • .XLS / .XLSX • .PPT / .PPTX • .PDF • Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)
Size of data	
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classified (available only to the partner that gathered the data and the EC, if requested), • Closed (available only for consortium members and the EC, if requested),
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI shared folder • APRE server

Task 6.2 Data Management Plan and Ethics

Data description	DECLARATION ON ETHICAL STANDARDS AND DATA PROTECTION by CATALISI Partners
Data collector	APRE
Data source/origin	External sources
Purpose of data collection	
Type of data collected	Financial/administrative data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .PDF
Size of data	
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closed (available only for consortium members and the EC, if requested),
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI shared folder

Task 6.3 Coordination and animation of the Community of Practice

Data description	Name, surname, email, role, country, affiliation, background, expertise of CATALISI CoP Members (within CoP Database). Pictures, Biographies and Social media accounts. Agendas, minutes and recordings of MML events organized with CoP
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	Members. Mapping of previously funded projects and relevant organisations.
Data collector	APRE and F6S
Data source/origin	Stakeholder mapping, Open call for members, Microsoft form, Reporting tools, pre-existing data.
Purpose of data collection	Build and then involve a Community of Practice (CoP) in the CATALISI activities in order to maximise the impact of the results (T.6.3)
Type of data collected	Technical data Stakeholders data
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .DOC / .DOCX • .XLS / .XLSX • .PPT / .PPTX • .PDF • Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG) • Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)
Size of data	
Open availability of produced data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classified (available only to the partner that gathered the data and the EC, if requested) – personal data of CoP members • Open (publicly available) through a section of the CATALISI website on the CoP: https://catalisi.eu/community-of-practice-members/ (consent forms signed by all CoP members, agreeing to showcase their personal data on the website)
Data accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATALISI website • CATALISI Zenodo Community • CATALISI shared folder • Partner's server (APRE and F6S)

2.4 Data shared with third parties

Concrete steps have been taken by the CATALIS consortium to ensure that the data shared with third parties (particularly with the sister projects and through communication, dissemination and exploitation activities) is duly processed and protected. In specific:

- CATALISI signed a Collaboration Agreement with the sister projects (Accelerate_FutureHEI and aUPaEU) agreeing on joint dissemination and communication activities and mutual sharing of knowledge and information, ensuring protection of personal data and confidentiality of shared information that is not known to the public or has not yet been revealed (Appendix 4);
- CATALISI signed with aUPaEU an 'AGORA Platform Users Agreement' setting the rules for the integration of CATALISI acceleration services within the AGORA Platform and accessing the Platform for research, education and innovation purposes (Appendix 5).

In addition, in response to the interim review recommendation, the consortium incorporated new agreements and operational practices emerging from joint acceleration service developments, shared activities and coordinated communication efforts. All data-related processes reflect the evolving collaboration model within the project and also with external parties (e.g. sister and synergy projects, etc.), as presented below.

1. Shared Activities and Joint Developments

Common procedure for managing data and documentation arising from joint activities, including the co-development of acceleration services and shared operational tasks.

All data generated through these collaborative processes, e.g. methodologies, blueprints/drafts/boards, datasets, KPIs and technical documentation, is stored in the project's shared repository under clearly defined access rights (access to the repository and certain folders is granted by the PC to designated representatives of the partners).

Ownership, co-ownership, and reuse conditions for jointly produced materials are as to the signed Consortium agreement and/or bilateral agreements among the project partners (when applicable) as long as the latter do not contradict the consortium agreement. Partners contributing to joint developments are granted shared access to relevant datasets and working documents, following the project's agreed version-control and traceability rules.

Procedure for the exchange of information with sister projects, particularly in relation to the development of joint policy briefs.

Information relevant to these joint outputs is typically exchanged via email between the CATALISI Project Coordinator and the coordinators or designated representatives of the sister projects. To support structured collaboration, a dedicated, access-restricted repository folder has been created and is maintained by the CATALISI Project Coordinator. This folder serves as a shared space for the exchange and storage of draft policy briefs, background documents, data contributions, and other materials relevant to joint work.

Access to this folder is explicitly granted only to the project coordinators of the participating sister projects (and appointed by them representatives). All documents stored within this space follow the project's classification and version-control rules, ensuring traceability, confidentiality where required, and consistency across all jointly developed materials.

Ownership, co-ownership, and reuse conditions for jointly produced materials are as to the signed MoU with the sister projects.

2. Sharing of Internal Documents

Consolidated framework for the classification, storage, and exchange of internal documents.

All project materials are categorised as *Public*, *Internal*, or *Confidential*, with corresponding handling rules. A structured, access-controlled repository (maintained by the PC on SharePoint) is used for storing deliverables, templates, meeting minutes, working drafts, and other project-relevant documents. Versioning conventions and naming protocols have been harmonised across the consortium to ensure consistency and traceability. Partners are required to upload updated versions of documents to the shared repository to maintain a single source of truth.

3. External Communication Materials

Procedures for managing communication and dissemination materials

All external communication outputs (including press releases, social media assets, brochures, infographics, videos, event materials, and public presentations) are stored in a dedicated shared folder (usually within WP5) with appropriate metadata and usage rights.

The approval workflow for communication materials is as follows:

(1) Before publication, materials undergo validation by:

- the Communication & Dissemination Manager at F6S,
- the relevant content-owning partners, and
- the Coordinator (where required for sensitive topics).

Licensing conditions for public materials follow the project's open-access policy (e.g., CC BY 4.0), while internal-only communication assets remain restricted to consortium use.

In addition, the datasets containing personal data obtained for the purpose of publishing materials or presenting a person on the project website (e.g. the CoP members, showcasing the acceleration services provided by the partners, publishing news or articles, etc.) are restricted to the access of the partners handling the process (collecting the information and processing the uploading), while the published data is limited by the signed consent forms obtained by the third parties.

4. Data Generated Through Joint Events and Activities

Procedures for handling data generated during events, workshops, webinars, and other outreach activities.

This includes participant lists, consent forms, feedback surveys, recordings, and photos. All personal data is processed in accordance with GDPR requirements, with explicit consent collected for any data intended for dissemination or long-term storage.

The project collects and processes several categories of data in the context of joint events and activities organised with partners, stakeholders, and sister/synergy projects. These activities may include workshops, webinars, co-creation sessions, conferences, and dissemination activities. The types of data generated typically include participant lists, registration information, attendance records, feedback forms, event evaluations, photographs, and audio/video recordings.

All personal data collected during these events is processed in accordance with GDPR principles and the project's internal data-protection procedures. Participation in events is voluntary, and individuals are informed in advance about the type of data being collected, the purpose of processing, and their rights under GDPR. Explicit consent is obtained whenever required (particularly for the use of photographs, video recordings, or quotes in communication and dissemination materials). Consent forms or digital consent mechanisms are stored securely and linked to the corresponding event documentation.

Access to personal data generated through events is restricted to authorised members of the consortium who require it for reporting, communication, or evaluation purposes. Selected information might be occasionally provided to the representatives of the sister/synergy project wherever this is absolutely necessary for the purposes of the joint organization and / or reporting of the event or communication activity. Participant lists and feedback data are stored solely by the organizing partner/s in controlled internal folders with appropriate access rights, while recordings and visual materials are stored in designated media repositories with restricted access. Only anonymised or aggregated data is used for reporting, analysis, or inclusion in public deliverables.

Retention periods for event-related personal data follow the project's data-retention policy and legal obligations. Personal data is kept only for the duration necessary to fulfil reporting and audit requirements and is then securely deleted. Publicly disseminated materials (e.g., event photos or recordings) include only individuals who have provided explicit consent for such use.

5. Long-Term Preservation and Accessibility

Long-term preservation strategy for communication materials, public deliverables, and other outputs of lasting relevance.

Public materials will be archived on the project website and/or open repositories (e.g., Zenodo), ensuring accessibility beyond the project's lifetime. Internal documents of long-term value will remain stored in the consortium's shared repository with sustained access for partners after project completion, subject to the Consortium agreement. Communication and Dissemination materials that are considered project results and/or evidence for an implemented activity/ achieved results will be stored for a period of minimum 5 years after the project end.

6. Handling of Personal Data for Reimbursement of External Project Representatives

In the context of reimbursing travel expenses for representatives of sister and synergy projects (or other external representatives), the consortium processed a limited set of personal data provided voluntarily by the individuals concerned. This data typically included identification details, contact information, travel documentation, and bank details required for reimbursement. All such data was handled exclusively by the partner bearing the costs, (e.g. the project Coordinator PC, the F6S financial team), following the Travel policy of the partner and the project's established data-protection procedures. This personal data was collected solely for the purpose of fulfilling contractual reimbursement obligations and was processed under the principles of data minimisation, purpose limitation, and confidentiality. Access to the data was strictly restricted to authorised personnel within the partner bearing the costs (within the financial team), and all exchanges took place through secure communication channels (organizational emails, voice verification by phone before payment). Personal data was stored in controlled internal folders with restricted access and will be retained only for the legally required duration for financial reporting and audit purposes. After this period, the data will be securely deleted in accordance with GDPR and the consortium's internal data-retention policy. No personal data collected for reimbursement purposes was shared with other partners or external entities beyond what is legally required for financial administration.

7. Data Exchange Between CATALISI and Sister Projects

The consortium has established a structured procedure for the exchange of information with sister projects, particularly in cases where publicly available project data is required to support cross-project platforms or joint technical developments. An example is the provision of CATALISI project information to the aUPaEU project for the configuration of the Agora platform.

Only information that is already publicly accessible through the CATALISI website, published deliverables, or official communication channels is shared with sister projects. This includes project descriptions, partner profiles, acceleration service provided by the partners, public deliverables, communication materials, and other non-confidential content. No personal data or internal documents are exchanged as part of this process.

Requests for information from sister projects are coordinated through the CATALISI Project Coordinator and DEC responsible partner (G6S), who validates that the requested content is public and appropriate for reuse. Once validated, the information is transmitted via secure email or through a dedicated shared folder created for cross-project collaboration. In case of a folder, it is ensured with controlled access exclusively to the coordinators (or technical person/s assigned to the joint configuration of the platform) of the participating sister projects. All documents stored in this space follow the project's version-control and classification rules. Another approach used is the direct upload of information (already publicly available as explained above) on the sister project platform by the DEC responsible partner at CATALISI (F6S).

2.5 Data storage and backup

With the aim to follow the FAIR principles and to stimulate the collaboration among partners, a few data storage tools have been selected. The selection was made having in mind the purposes and the end-users of the data stored, divided in tools appropriate for internal use and daily project activities, and tools for guaranteeing the long-term storage of CATALISI data.

CATALISI storage tools used to carry out daily project activities (NOT appropriate for long-term storing of data):

- ✓ **Microsoft SharePoint:** is a file hosting service and synchronization service operated by Microsoft as part of its web version of Office. It is a private space, created for the project activities, used by all beneficiaries to share working files and store temporary master copy of raw data that should be available for use by other beneficiaries for data processing.
- ✓ **Local drives, company cloud storage and external portable storage devices:** these are storage facilities that do not fall under surveillance of this data management plan. These are very common and convenient for individual short-term storage of data.

CATALISI storage tool used for long-term storing of data and to guarantee the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data generated by project, is **the CATALISI community in ZENODO**: where CATALISI datasets will be stored.

Link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/catalisiproject/?page=1&size=20%C3%B9>

Data files are versioned. The uploaded data is archived as a Submission Information Package. Derivatives of data files are generated, but original content is never modified. All data files are stored in CERN Data Centres, primarily Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, which is backed up to tape on a nightly basis. All data files are stored along with a MD5 checksum of the file content. Files are regularly checked against their checksums to assure that file content remains constant. Each beneficiary has the possibility to upload the data produced by their project activities in the community and a moderator will validate it. Each data-set will have a readme file. ZENODO is compliant with the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH), a widely used protocol for harvesting metadata.

2.6 Data Findable

All data are documented to help interested users to clearly find them and reuse them. For this reason, descriptive and substantive (i.e. how the data should be read or interpreted) metadata will be elaborated and described in a "readme.txt" file complementing each dataset (see Table 2).

TABLE 2 METADATA INCLUDED IN THE README FILE OF CATALISI DATA

Creator*	Main partner name involved in producing the data.
Title*	Name or title by which the dataset is known.
Contributor	Institution where the data was created or collected. A person or organization responsible for making contributions to the dataset.

Publisher	A holder of the data (including archives appropriate) or institution which submitted the work. Any others may be listed as contributors.
Publication year*	The year when the data was or will be made publicly available.
Date created*	Date the resource itself was put together; this could be a date range or a single date.
Description*	Concise description of the contents of the dataset. Describe the research objective, type of research, method of data collection and type of data.
Subject	Subject, keyword, or key phrase describing the resource.
Temporal coverage	Indicate the dates to which the data refer. Enter the year or beginning and ending dates.
Spatial coverage	Describe the geographic area to which the data refer (e.g. municipality, town/city, region, country). The geographic coordinates of the area may be included, if desired.
Identifier	Zenodo automatically assigns a DOI to a dataset once the entire deposit procedure has been completed. In some cases, a dataset may be known by one or more other (persistent) identifiers.
Language*	The primary language of the resource.
Link to publication	Include the web addresses or DOIs for any publication, important internal reports or other datasets that are related to your dataset.

File naming & Identifiers

In CATALISI project, an identifier is used as a reference number or name for a data object. The identifier is a key part of our documentation and metadata. Table 3 shows the codes that can be used for making identifiers.

TABLE 3 EXAMPLES OF FILES IDENTIFICATION

Description	Deliverables	Meetings	Conferences/Events
First Letters	CATALISI	CATALISI	CATALISI
Underscore	_	_	_
Next letters	Deliverable number (Dx.y) [x=WP number, y=deliverable number]	Type of document (i.e. Agenda, Minutes, Presentation). In case of presentations, mention WP number as well.	Event title
Underscore	_	_	_
Next letters	Short explanatory title for the document (or acronym)	Location and date of the meeting separated by underscore	Location and date of the meeting separated by underscore
Underscore	_	_	_
Next letters	Short name of organisation leading the deliverable	Short name of organisation and initials of presenter	Short name of organisation and initials of presenter
Underscore	_	_	_
Last letters	"v" and number of revision of this specific report [v0.1=draft version, v1.0=final version]	"v" and number of revision of this specific report [v0.1=draft version, v1.0=final version]	"v" and number of revision of this specific report [v0.1=draft version, v1.0=final version]

2.7 Data Accessible

The main part of raw and processed data generated by the project will be accessible to all consortium partners. It will be stored in CATALISI SharePoint dedicated space. Only members of the consortium, after validation from the group administrator (i.e. APRE), can access this space. The public data will be accessible by ZENODO Community.

The data containing personal data and the data gathered through questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, workshops and through other data gathering methods used during the project will be anonymised by default; for the purposes of the project's activities (specifically stakeholders engagement related activities, as a crucial element of the project), with prior expressed consent to share personal data, they will be used and will not be made accessible for any third party.

Raw data like interview and audio files will be shared within the consortium partners and with external open repositories only upon agreement of the participants (agreement via informed consent) and in an anonymised form. In the case of sharing the data in an open repository, the following formats would be shared: audio files, transcripts, aggregated files, interview guidelines.

Confidential data and data collected for internal purposes will be stored in the secure facilities of the organization responsible for collecting the data and will be retained for two years after the end of project. If requested and agreed by the participants, data can be shared with other consortium members through the online repository.

In the case of data that cannot be accessible to public, it will be stored in ZENODO (to preserve it) but only the metadata will be public (in CC 0).

Details concerning the ownership, transfer and dissemination of projects results are defined in section 8 of the CATALISI Consortium Agreement and shall be followed accordingly. The relevant rules of the Grant Agreement, in specific Article 13, Article 15, Article 16 and Annex 5, are also relevant and apply accordingly.

2.8 Data sharing and reuse

CATALISI beneficiaries will be the main users of data produced in the project. In CATALISI all data may be classified into open, sensitive and closed. Access depends on the classification of the data.

- ✓ **Open data** is applied when data have no IP restrictions and will be openly available and re-usable, acknowledged by citing the data set. This is the case of the data in the Public deliverables.
- ✓ **Sensitive** (or confidential/restricted) **data** may be made available after any identifying information has been removed.
- ✓ **Closed data** are not available for sharing.

In any case, the open CATALISI data will have the CC-BY license.

Details concerning the ownership, transfer and dissemination of projects results are defined in section 8 of the CATALISI Consortium Agreement and shall be followed accordingly. The relevant rules of the Grant Agreement, in specific Article 13, Article 15, Article 16 and Annex 5, are also relevant and apply accordingly.

2.9 Data preservation and archiving

All relevant obtained data will be preserved and archived in ZENODO for long term archiving. All data and items on ZENODO will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

3 ETHICS AND PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION

3.1 Applicable legal framework

The European Union has developed the EU Data Protection and Privacy legal framework² which aims at ensuring that personal data enjoy a high standard of protection everywhere in the EU and that persons or organizations collecting and managing personal information must protect it from misuse. One of the main pillars of this legal framework is Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data - GDPR. The Regulation applies to all entities established in the EU (or branches established in the EU) that process personal data as part of their activities, regardless of where the data is processed; and entities established outside the EU offering goods/services to individuals in the EU or monitoring the behaviour in the EU of these individuals.

In addition to GDPR, there are other sectorial legal acts that must be considered when implementing EU research projects:

- Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purpose of prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences,
- Directive 2000/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2000 on certain legal aspects of information society services, in particular electronic commerce in the Internal Market,
- Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector.

In this framework, with regards to personal data in the context of project implementation, the CATALISI consortium (as whole as well as each single Beneficiary) guarantees that privacy data will be treated in compliance with ethical and legal requirements, with the data protection principles of lawfulness, fairness and transparency in data processing, as well as purpose limitation, data minimization, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity and confidentiality, and fully agrees that the protection of personal data is a priority.

At this purpose, the project consortium defined data protection roles and responsibilities and provides information and informed consent for data processing. In particular, Beneficiary will request informed consent to disseminate such data for scientific and training purposes. At the same time, informed consent can never legitimize the use of data in an open access environment considering that the purposes for further use of data are unknown. In such cases hence data will be kept confidential. Last but not least, no transfer of personal data outside the EU is foreseen as part of the project's implementation.

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection_en

3.2 Principle of personal data processing

According to Art. 4(1) of GDPR, **personal data** 'means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person'. Personal data protection typically covers: names and surnames, home and email address, an identification card number, location data and IP address or a cookie ID. **Processing of personal data** is defined in Art. 4(2) of the Regulation and means 'any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organization, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction'.

In its Art. 5, the GDPR provides for the **principles of personal data processing**, stating that personal data must be:

- 'processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject ('lawfulness, fairness and transparency');
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes (...) ('purpose limitation');
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed ('data minimisation');
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay ('accuracy');
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed (...) ('storage limitation');
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures ('integrity and confidentiality').

In order to fulfill the GDPR requirements, there is a set of indications that each CATALISI Beneficiary dealing with data processing will respect during the project implementation:

1) Consent

The consent should be given by an individual (data subject) in a free, specific, informed and unambiguous manner, by way of a request presented in clear and plain language. Moreover, the consent should be given by an affirmative act, such as checking a box online or signing a form.

2) Providing transparent information

Individuals must be clearly informed on who is processing their personal data as well as what data will be processed, why and how. In addition to the above information, individuals should be also informed about who will receive the data, how long the data will be stored, the individual's data protection rights (i.e. right to access, correct, erase, restrict, object, portability, etc.), whether there is a statutory or contractual obligation to provide the data and how consent can be withdrawn.

3) Ensuring the right to access and the right to data portability

Individuals must have the right to request access to their personal data, free of charge and in an accessible format. In addition, when the processing is based on consent or a contract, the individual can ask for their personal data to be returned or transmitted to another company (right to portability).

4) Ensuring the right to erasure (right to be forgotten)

An individual has the right to request the data controller to erase their personal data, such as when the data is no longer needed to fulfil the processing purpose. The data controller is not obliged to comply with such request if: the processing is necessary to respect one's freedom of expression and information, they must keep the personal data to comply with a legal obligation; there are other reasons of public interest to keep the personal data, such as public health or scientific and historical research purposes; they need to keep the personal data to establish a legal claim.

5) Ensuring the right to correct and right to object

If an individual thinks that their personal data is incorrect, incomplete or inaccurate, they have the right to have it rectified or completed without undue delay

6) Obligation to appoint a Data Protection Officer

An entity must appoint a DPO when: it regularly or systematically monitors individuals or process special categories of data; this processing is a core business activity; and it does it on a large scale. In the case of CATALISI, Beneficiaries provided to the Coordinator declarations on the basis of the letter template in Appendix 1 (if they do not have a DPO) or on the basis of the template in Appendix 2 (if they appointed a DPO).

7) Obligation of data protection by design and by default

In order to minimize privacy risks and increase trust, a data controller³ must take all necessary steps (e.g. pseudonymization) to implement the data protection principles and protect the rights of individuals (data protection by design). In accordance with the obligation of data protection by default, the entity processing personal data should ensure that the most privacy friendly setting is the default setting.

8) Obligation to provide proper notification in the case of a data breach

In case a data breach occurs and the breach poses a risk to individual rights and freedoms, the entity processing personal data should notify the relevant Data Protection Authority within 72 hours after becoming aware of the breach. If the data breach poses a high risk to those affected, the entity may also be required to inform all individuals affected by the data breach.

Details on specific measures that will be taken by each CATALISI Beneficiary to safeguard the rights and freedoms of CATALISI data subjects/research participants and the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to their personal data are provided in Appendix 2 in the '**Declaration on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection**' of each Beneficiary, in the part related to the privacy policy of the Beneficiary.

3.2.1 Informed consent procedure

Participation of third parties in the CATALISI project is voluntary and individual participants agree to participate in project activities (both online and physical) based on the invitation issued. Along with an invitation, participants receive an informed consent and agree to participate, before the commencement of any project activity requiring their involvement, in compliance with GDPR.

The documentation related to informed consent will be provided in the language and terms intelligible to the participants. To this end, before each event involving participants, they will be asked to sign an informed consent and will be fully briefed, in the informed consent, as to their data protection rights, including:

- who is responsible for the treatment of data;
- who is the data protection officer to whom the participant can claim their rights;
- specification of which data are collecting (personal data or other);
- how the consortium will deal with the data (collection, storage, etc.);
- for which purpose data (research and no other purpose; explicitly excluding commercial purpose) are collecting,

³ According to Art. 4(7) GDPR, 'controller' means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law.

- what are the consequences of the denial of the use of data;
- the possibility to withdraw from the use of data and the consequences;
- to whom data will be transmitted;
- the time of storage of data;
- the place of storage and the tools available to guarantee security;
- the rights of the data owner (to access, modify, rectify, cancel data, right to object, and to ask restriction of processing);
- risks or benefits of participation.

Participants will not be placed in any situation in which there is a likelihood of physical, mental, or emotional harm. No sensitive data⁴ will be collected, processed, or stored.

Below and example of the sentence that the partner organizing the event and responsible for collecting the personal data, will insert in the informed consent in the proper Language:

*"Your personal information, including your name and email address, will not be used by CATALISI to identify you and will not be made available publicly. Your personal information, including your name and email address, will be used to communicate with you about [insert the aim]. CATALISI will not sell, rent or exchange any personal information supplied by you to any third party. Your personal information will only be used for CATALISI purposes and only until the end of the project (31 December 2025), and stored on [insert where]. By filling in this form, you agree to the use of your image (video and photos) for CATALISI reporting and promotional purposes, in the context of European Commission obligations regarding reports and Dissemination activities (Grant Agreement, art.29 "Dissemination of results" and art.20 "Reporting"). *Your name displayed during online meetings may be showcased in promotional materials and reporting. If you wish for this data to remain anonymous, please change the displayed name. In addition, you may turn off your camera if you do not wish your image to be displayed. CATALISI privacy policy available [indicate where is available] For any inquiries reach out to us via email: [insert where]."*

3.3 Data processing

The data processed in CATALISI is divided into two categories:

- ✓ Personal data (typically name, surname, date of birth, gender, level of education, professional affiliation and contact information);

⁴ Data relating to racial or ethnic origin, religious or philosophical beliefs, political opinion, health including biometric and genetic data, sexual preferences, data relating to criminal convictions and offences or related security measures.

- ✓ Professional views on the themes related to the project and discussed during project activities, excluding sensitive data.

Personal data is necessary for ensuring a person's participation in the project and to comply with mandatory legal obligations under European Union legislation, as well as for processing under consent and for the purposes of legitimate interests as follows:

- ✓ To process any application a person makes to participate in any of the CATALISI events or activities;
- ✓ To process any request for information supplied by the project and to ensure effective communication;
- ✓ To organize and promote project events and activities;
- ✓ To send health and safety and other relevant event information for any CATALISI events and activities that persons are participating in;
- ✓ To notify persons of events, activities, publications, and services that may be of interest to them.

Information about professional views on the themes related to the project will be collected solely for research purposes necessary to carry out project activities.

The above data collected from participants will be stored on computer media of the consortium partner collecting this data (typically, a partner organizing a given activity) and protected against unauthorized access and use according to the internal rules of the respective partner, which must be in line with applicable EU and national legislation. Personal data of participants to CATALISI events will be shared with other consortium partners by the partner collecting this data only under explicit consent of each participant.

Where possible, any identifiable information will be encrypted or minimized. That means that only strictly necessary data will be collected, processed, and stored.

The consortium will retain the collected data for as long as it is necessary:

- To carry out CATALISI events and activities;
- For establishment or defense of legal claims that could be made against the consortium;
- To comply with legal obligations under EU law.

Any data collected within the project will be kept for a maximum of five years after the end of the project and will then be destroyed by each project partner in relation to the data they processed during the project duration. More information about data management is included in these deliverable Chapter 2 'Data Management Plan'.

3.4 CATALISI website

For the purposes of the GDPR, CATALISI website dedicates a specific area to the 'Privacy Policy'. The privacy policy comprises the following sections:

1. Policy scope
2. Why and how is ensure compliance with

3. Who must comply
4. What are the data protection principles and rules
5. Personal data collected and how are used them
6. Cookies and third parties
7. How personal data is stored
8. How long personal data are kept
9. Data Breaches
10. Rights as data subjects with respect to per personal data
11. Time limit
12. Data controller and contact details
13. How to complain
14. Changes to privacy policy information

3.5 Join controller Agreement

Where necessary, the Beneficiaries agreed (art. 4. Point 4 of the Consortium Agreement) to cooperate in order to enable one another to fulfil legal obligations arising under applicable data protection laws (the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and relevant national data protection law applicable to said Party) within the scope of the performance and administration of the Project.

In particular, the Beneficiaries shall, where necessary, conclude a separate data processing, data sharing and/or joint controller agreement before any data processing or data sharing takes place.

4 QUALITY MANAGEMENT PLAN

4.1 Quality Management Objectives

The **Quality Plan** (QP) in CATALISI has these two main objectives:

- ✓ ensure smooth implementation and timely completion of the project activities; and
- ✓ guarantee the quality of the activities and deliverables of the project in line with the contractual obligations enclosed in the Grant Agreement and in compliance with the Consortium Agreement signed by all CATALISI beneficiaries.

The Plan provides the description of the management structure, describes the responsibilities of the partners, defines the procedures for ensuring the quality of project deliverables and for communication within and outside the consortium as well as presents procedures for progress monitoring and reporting.

All project partners commit to be in compliance with the requirements described in the QP, having in mind that this Plan does not replace the Grant Agreement signed with the EC, its Annexes, and the Consortium Agreement of the project, which remain the main source of reference for the project.

4.2 CATALISI Main management bodies

The CATALISI management structure is composed of following main management bodies:

- **The Project coordinator (APRE)** is in charge for the financial, administrative and operative management and coordination of the consortium and project activities. The Project Coordinator is responsible for: 1) the overall technical, administrative and financial co-ordination of the project; 2) the control of the project scheduling and achievements; 3) the generation of corrective actions, if needed, with the support of the Steering Committee and with the agreement of the General Assembly; 4) the submission to the Commission of the deliverables and regular reports of progress and resource expenditure; 5) the verification of the milestones achieved; 6) the internal smooth communication among all partners; 7) the organization and chairing of the General Assembly, the Steering Committee and the Advisory Board meetings .
- **The Steering Committee (SC)** is composed by the WP leaders and is chaired by the Project Coordinator (PC). Its main task is to monitor project progress in relation to each Work Package, using milestones, deliverables and key performance indicators as instruments to better understand project advancements and which further steps are to be accomplished in order to ensure an effective progress of the whole project. Decisions shall be taken by a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast, with the exception of decisions listed in Section 6.3.1.2 of the Consortium Agreement, which shall require a unanimous vote by the General Assembly. The WP leaders are responsible for supervising their WPs and ensuring that milestones and deliverables are reached on time. The SC will report to the General Assembly.

- **The General Assembly (GA)** is the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium. The GA is composed of at least one representative of each partner institution and is chaired by the Project Coordinator. Each partner is responsible to carry out the activities described in the work plan and to answer to the Project Coordinator requests on time. The Project Coordinator organises the meetings with the GA, chairs the meetings, prepares the agenda and the minutes. Each partner's representative has one vote. The decisions are taken by consensus or by majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast, with the exception of decisions listed in Section 6.3.1.2 of the Consortium Agreement which shall be taken always by unanimous.

TABLE 4 LIST OF WP LEADER.

Work Package	WP Leader
WP1 - Acting-LL co-creation	ENoLL
WP2 - Knowledge sharing and mutual learning programme	APRE
WP3 - Design, Coaching and Sustainability	EY
WP4 - Evaluation and Impact Assessment	UCC
WP5 - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation	F6S
WP6 - Project Management	APRE

The roles and responsibilities of each partner are described in detail within Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement, namely the Description of the Action (DoA) and the role and responsibility of these management body are described in Section 6 of the Consortium Agreement. All partners should take the necessary measures and provide all necessary resources for the on-time and smooth elaboration of their tasks and responsibilities.

4.3 CATALISI Deliverables

According to the DoA, every deliverable is under the responsibility of a specific Lead Beneficiary and is the outcome of a specific task, linked to a work package. The Lead Beneficiary responsible for the deliverable guarantees the quality, completeness, and timely submission of the document to the Coordinator who must submit it via the Portal to the granting authority. All beneficiaries must give the contribution to the drafting of the deliverable when required.

4.3.1 File format

All deliverables must follow the established CATALISI deliverable template, which has been draft by WP6 Leader (F6S) and shared with all partners in the project Teams Group, in dedicated folder "**5. Templates & basic documents**".

4.3.2 File naming

In respect to electronic files, the following guidelines in terms of deliverable name will be followed:

- File name should preferably not exceed 40 characters. The deliverable number and official name as stated in the Grant Agreement should be part of the file name.
- The author of the file puts the name of his/her organisation in the file name.
- The file name contains the date of the last modification.
- In the case of a deliverable revision by another partner, the revising partner adds, as the end of the file name, an abbreviation '_rev' and the name of his/her organisation. This rule does not apply in case a document is revised simultaneously by partners.
- The file name contains at the end of file name, an abbreviation 'Vox' indicating the number of the version in case a deliverable needs to be modified during the project duration.

An example on applying the above naming rule of electronic files is shown below:

Del. N.	Short name official	Author name organization	Date last modification
---------	---------------------	--------------------------	------------------------

D3.1_CoachingAndMentoring_EY_04.04.2023

Del. N.	Short name official	Author name organization	Date last modification	Rev author
---------	---------------------	--------------------------	------------------------	------------

D3.1_CoachingAndMentoring_EY_04.04.2023_revAPRE

Del. N.	Short name official	Author name organization	Date last modification	Version
---------	---------------------	--------------------------	------------------------	---------

D3.1_CoachingAndMentoring_EY_04.04.2023_V01

D3.1_CoachingAndMentoring_EY_04.04.2024_V02

4.3.3 Quality assurance procedure

The standard quality process is assurance through the following four steps:

Steps	What	Who	When
1	A draft deliverable is shared for revision in the form of an online document, saved in the concerned WP folder in the Team Group in order to enable access of multiple persons simultaneously.	By Lead Beneficiary responsible for the deliverable, to the other supporters and the relevant WP leaders contributors.	At latest 15 working days before the submission deadline.
2	Comments and feedback are provided (they shall be always provided in the track-changes mode).	By Task Supporters, the WP leaders, and, if relevant, other internal reviewers.	Whitin maximum of 5 working days
3	The comments, including, if necessary, further consultations with the Task Supporters and the WP leader, are addressed	By Lead Beneficiary responsible for the deliverable	Maximum of 5 working days
4	The revised deliverable is sent to a reviewer chosen among partners, different from the person who has written, edited and contributed to the document.	By Coordinator	At least 4/5 days before the submission deadline
5	The consolidated documents will be sent to the coordinator	By the reviewer	One-two days before the submission.
5	The final deliverable in the Funding & Tenders Portal is submitted.	By the Coordinator, who is the only one responsible for submitting deliverables in the Portal.	On submission date defined in the DoA.

TABLE 5 QUALITY ASSUTANCE PROCEDURE STEPS

The table below presents all project deliverables, the respective deliverable's leaders and dates relevant for the quality assurance process and for the deliverable submission. It should be noted that these are the suggested latest dates. However, Lead Beneficiaries are encouraged to speed up the quality assurance process and submit first versions of their respective deliverables before the indicated dates, if possible and feasible.

TABLE 6 INDICATIVE SCHEDULE FOR INTERNAL REVISION

Del. N.	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary	Step 1 (15 days at latest)	Step 2 (within 5 days)	Step 3 (by 5 days)	Step 4 (4-5 days at ealier)	Step 5 (submission date)
D3.1	Coaching and mentoring framework	EY	06/04/2023	14/04/2023	21/04/2023	28/04/2023	30/04/2023
D2.1	Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning Plan	APRE	12/06/2023	19/06/2023	23/06/2023	26/06/2023	30/06/2023
D5.1	First Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Sustainability plans	F6S	12/06/2023	19/06/2023	23/06/2023	26/06/2023	30/06/2023
D6.1	Data and Quality Management Plan	APRE	12/06/2023	19/06/2023	23/06/2023	26/06/2023	30/06/2023
D1.1	Acting-LLs needs assessment and 4-helix ecosystem	ENoLL	10/08/2023	17/08/2023	24/08/2023	28/08/2023	31/08/2023
D1.2	Acting-LLs action plans	ENoLL	11/12/2023	14/12/2023	20/12/2023	26/12/2023	31/12/2023
D3.3	Predictive Study	EY	11/12/2023	14/12/2023	20/12/2023	26/12/2023	31/12/2023
D6.2	First Policy brief	APRE	11/12/2023	14/12/2023	20/12/2023	26/12/2023	31/12/2023
D4.1	Evaluation and impact assessment plan	UCC	09/04/2024	16/04/2024	23/04/2023	24/04/2024	30/04/2024
D2.2	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Report	APRE	09/06/2025	16/06/2025	20/06/2025	24/06/2025	30/06/2025
D1.3	Acting-LLs evaluation report	ENoLL	05/12/2025	12/12/2025	19/12/2025	21/12/2025	31/12/2025
D2.3	Twinning schemes report	APRE	05/12/2025	12/12/2025	19/12/2025	21/12/2025	31/12/2025
D3.2	Collection of transformational pathways	EY	05/12/2025	12/12/2025	19/12/2025	21/12/2025	31/12/2025
D4.2	Monitoring and implementation report (including impact assessment toolkit)	UCC	05/12/2025	12/12/2025	19/12/2025	21/12/2025	31/12/2025
D5.2	Final Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Sustainability plans	F6S	05/12/2025	12/12/2025	19/12/2025	21/12/2025	31/12/2025
D6.3	Final Policy brief	APRE	05/12/2025	12/12/2025	19/12/2025	21/12/2025	31/12/2025

4.4 Communication

4.4.1 Internal communication among partners

The Coordinator has the main responsibility of ensuring smooth and effective internal communication. Communication among Beneficiaries will primarily take place through online communication means, namely emails and online calls and meetings.

A mailing list, featuring the relevant contact details for each Beneficiary has been created at M1, is available in the Teams Group (dedicated file "**Contacts.xlsx**"). It was regularly updated

to ensure that possible staff rotations are timely addressed and do not affect the project implementation. To that end, in the event of any change in the contact details or in the project team, partners should notify the Coordinator, who updates the mailing list accordingly and without due delay.

From the mailing list, two project emails have been created:

- catalisi@apre.it used for: General Events notice, Reporting activities, Amendments information, Annual meeting invitation, Notice social media updates; It is linked to the SharePoint space.
- catalisi_workteam@apre.it (underscore), constitutes the main email to communicate among task leader and team members about project activities, used (not exhaustive list) for day-to-day communication, consortium Monthly meetings, deliverable checks and feedback.

Whatever email is used, Beneficiaries always:

- use a narrative subject beginning with 'CATALISI'
- inform and update the partners on time about the work you are doing
- explain what is expected: is it feedback (from whom and by when), or is it just information,
- avoid attachments (if possible), save them in the concerned shared space (e.g., WP folder),
- Inform me and Laura if you want to add (or to remove) someone from your organization contacts, mentioning the role, the email and in which mailing list to be added.

As general rule, it seeks to circulate emails from CATALISI to all members no more than once per day, for not lose track of what's important and might overlook the emails that ask for timely contribution.

In relation to **internal meetings**, according to the Consortium Agreement and the Description of Action, the main meetings will be:

- ✓ WPLs meetings (only on line): these are operative meetings, once a month, to keep regularly updated team members working on the project about the ongoing activities.
- ✓ CATALISI General Assembly will convey at the kick-off meeting (M1) and once a year (preferable on-site) for ordinary meetings (at M12, M24 and M36). At any time upon request, any member of the Steering Committee or 1/3 of the Members of the General Assembly can convene for extraordinary meetings.
- ✓ CATALISI Steering Committee ordinary meetings are foreseen once a year at the conjunction with the General Assembly (if possible). Extraordinary meetings can be called at any time upon request of any Member of the Steering Committee.

APRE, as coordinator, is responsible for convening the meeting, for meetings' organisation, logistics and minute drafting. The Kick-off meeting was held in Rome on January 2023. The other General Assembly and Steering Committee meetings will be held in a place to be decided.

Communication concerning important issues and strategic decision-making (e.g. sending deliverables, planning meetings, reporting risks or deviations from the DOA, etc.), as well as any formal communication (e.g. project meetings), should be documented in writing (e.g. by preparing the meeting minutes, maintaining an electronic (e.g. emails) or paper copy records). **Informal communication** taking place between Beneficiaries and concerning less significant issues of every-day project implementation (through telephone, informal emails, etc.) may not be documented.

The Coordinator and the WP Leaders are expected to communicate regularly with the project partners so as to follow closely the project and work packages progress, and identify in time potential deviations. Close collaboration and communication between project partners is essential and will be encouraged by the Coordinator especially in cases where they have to cooperate in order to perform specific tasks.

4.4.2 External communication

Communication with the EC

The Coordinator (APRE) is the sole responsible for the communication with the Project Officer (PO) with respect to the project. Project partners should not contact the PO without previous discussion with APRE. Only in exceptional cases, and if the PO requires so, may a project partner directly contact the PO. In such a case the Coordinator shall be kept fully informed (in writing) about the content of the communication.

The Coordinator has the responsibility of submitting to the EC all reports and deliverables of the project. They also provide the EC with any additional information and/or clarification that have been requested by the EC services. Finally, the Coordinator will keep all Beneficiaries informed about any important communication with the EC.

Communication with third parties

Project partners may and should communicate with third parties (e.g. national authorities, local stakeholders, other EU-funded projects) within the context of the project. In all external communications, a reference to the project should be made (e.g. project acronym, EU programme, GA No, funded by European Union). More about external communication will be defined in the Communication Plan.

4.4.1 Complaints and conflict resolution

Each WP leader will immediately notify the Coordinator about any event or circumstance that may significantly affect the performance of the work executed in the frame of their work package (e.g. suggestions for considerable improvements and modifications/changes in the methodology, timetable, and task allocation, potential delays, disputes between partners, etc.). The Coordinator will be responsible for and will take the necessary steps to resolve the abovementioned issues by consulting with the relevant WP leaders, the Steering Committee, and any partner directly involved in the respective Work Package.

In the case of a dispute, the following Conflict Resolution Procedure will apply: i) the disputing parties will inform the respective WP leader, ii) if the WP leader is not able to resolve the problem, they will inform the Coordinator, iii) The Coordinator will discuss the issue with the SC and, after reaching an internal agreement, will get in contact with the disputing parties

aiming at implementing the agreed decision, iv) if the issue is still not solved, the matter will be taken for a virtual vote at an extraordinary GA virtual meeting.

Further details with respect to decision-making, conflict resolution as well as the management of internal administrative and financial issues are incorporated in the project's Consortium Agreement. When necessary, the Coordinator will inform the EC requesting feedback.

4.5 Progress reporting

4.5.1 Internal reporting

In the Consortium Agreement, the Beneficiaries agreed not to envisage intermediate internal reports during the first year, too close to the EC formal periodic report required at M12.

However one additional **internal interim report** will be carry out by 31 December 2024 (M24). This report will consist of a brief report on activities carried out and costs incurred. It will be submitted to the coordinator and shared internally 40 days after the end of that period. The aim of this intermediate reporting is to monitor the work performed by each partner, at guaranteeing a coordinated management of both project activities and resources, with the view to timely detection of risks to project implementation and effective resolution of identified problems.

For the purpose of collecting all necessary information in a uniform and coordinated manner, the Coordinator will prepare a dedicated internal reporting tools both for financial and technical information. The tools will be shared with each Beneficiary well in advance before the end of the concerned period. Each reporting tool provided by each Beneficiary will need to be reviewed and approved by the Coordinator. The financial data must reflect the activities described by each partner, meaning that, for example, if there are no activities reported in a specific task, there cannot be financial efforts declared in that task.

The Coordinator will store the collected reporting tools in a separate dedicated and secure file Coordinator's server and will share the final analyses with all consortium.

4.5.2 Reporting to EC

The Coordinator is responsible for the periodic reports that will be prepared with the contribution of all Beneficiaries and then officially submitted in the Funding and Tenders Portal.

Within CATALISI, two official reports are foreseen, namely on 31 December 2023 (M12) and at the end of the project, on 31 December 2025 (M36). The abovementioned reports will enclose information about how the project is progressing both from a technical and a financial point of view. All partners have part of the responsibility to deliver the reports, meaning that they have to send their inputs for the report to the Coordinator in due time when requested and, with reference to the technical report, each Work Package Leader is directly responsible for the elaboration of the chapters related to their respective WPs, also gathering contributions from the task leaders. All the steps and the relative deadlines will be summarized within precise and detailed communications from the Coordinator preceding each reporting period. The reports will be submitted by the Coordinator online on the official EC templates and they will include:

- an overview of the activities carried out in the concerned period,
- a description of the progress achieved towards the objectives and the milestones planned,
- the deliverables produced,
- the identification of possible problems faced and the corrective actions taken or planned,

- information and justification about the resources used/deployed by each beneficiary. Furthermore, according to the official Horizon Europe legal and financial rules.

The consortium will submit the periodic report to the EC and the final report within 60 days following the end of the reporting period.

APPENDIX 1 TEMPLATE FOR DECLARATION ON ETHICAL STANDARDS AND DATA PROTECTION (NO DPO)

Place and date

DECLARATION on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection

I, the undersigned, representing **Name of your organization**, with seat in **Address of your organization**, hereby certify that **Name of your organization**:

applies **ethical principles and guidelines** of Horizon Europe programme according to Article 19 of the Regulation (EU) 2021/695 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013,

applies **data protection rules** according to the Regulation (EU) [2016/679](#) of the European Parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR),

hereby confirm that **Name of your organisation** **does not designate a Data Protection Officer** because none of the criteria in Art. 37 sub. 1 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) are met in the case of **Name of your organisation**. Nevertheless, **Name of your organisation** has in place an internal regulation for personal data management and protection and related data privacy policy (see below) to safeguard the rights and freedoms of CATALISI data subjects/research participants, and included a privacy working group in its organization chart coordinated by **XXX (name, surname and email address of the relevant person)**

.....
Title and signature of the person signing the document

APPENDIX 2 – TEMPLATE FOR DECLARATION ON ETHICAL STANDARDS AND DATA PROTECTION (WITH DPO)

Place and date

DECLARATION on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection

I, the undersigned, representing **Name of your organization**, with seat in **Address of your organization**, hereby certify that **Name of your organization**:

- applies **ethical principles and guidelines** of Horizon Europe programme according to Article 19 of the Regulation (EU) 2021/695 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013,
- applies data protection rules according to the Regulation (EU) **2016/679** of the European Parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).
- hereby confirm that **Name of your organisation** designated a Data Protection Officer: **Name and Surname of the DPO and his/her email address**
- hereby confirm that **Name of your organization** has in place an internal regulation for personal data management and protection and related data privacy policy (see below) to safeguard the rights and freedoms of CATALISI data subjects/research participants.

.....
Title and signature of the person signing the document

APPENDIX 3 – DATASETS USED FOR COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPOLITATION activities

EVENT REGISTRATION AND PARTICIPATION DATASETS

The project organised and run a series of events where it was necessary for participants to register.

1. Data capture

Participant registration for an event was done using an online registration form or in-person at the event. The information collected was the same independently of the registration being on or offline. Information collected was the minimum needed to generate statistics regarding participation at the event. When relevant, consent for usage of participants' image and audio in dissemination actions was also be collected. Participant registration was collected for every event run in the project.

In physical events, attendees were requested to sign attendance sheets or similar documents. Attendance sheets included a column that allows participants to mark their consent preference in relation to their image and information being publicly displayed.

2. Data storage

Information related to participants' registration was stored on the project's documentation repository to enable the long-term storage and access to data by consortium members. Information was stored according to each event organised in the project. Information was stored as it is received by the project team.

All files sent to the repository comply with the locations, names and permissions defined in the D6.1 - Data Management Plan.

3. Data quality assurance

The task leader/s was/were responsible for verifying that all required information is provided by participants, that it is stored and that instructions in the informed consents are enforced.

4. Utility and re-use

The registration dataset/s was/were used by consortium members to increase participants' engagement in the project. It also served to generate aggregated or anonymized statistics and reports about the participants.

Upon specific consent by the registrants, the dataset were occasionally used to communicate other events or initiatives organised by the CATALISI project or other projects that pursue a similar objective.

5. Data sharing

Upon specific consent by the registrants, names and emails were occasionally shared with other funded projects that pursue a similar objective to that of CATALISI project.

The EC might be informed of the number and general characterisation of the participants in official reports.

6. Archiving and preservation

The CATALISI consortium will retain generated data until five years after the balance of the project is paid or longer if there are ongoing procedures (such as audits, investigations or litigation). In this case, the data will be kept until they end.

OTHER EVENTS PARTICIPATION DATASETS

The project organised activities for which there was no registration form, and where for dissemination and/or reporting purposes it was useful to collect images and audio recordings of participants for dissemination actions. Examples of activities are: interviews, focus groups, work meetings, and round tables.

1. Data capture

Consent for usage of participants' image and audio recordings in the project was requested via a dedicated form collected through an F6S form or via email by another partner in charge of the activity. The partner in charge of the event collected the consent forms. The consent forms describe the purposes of the data collection and how the data will be used, and contain checkboxes for the participant to mark their preferences. Participants were informed that they can withdraw their consent by emailing the project explicitly stating this, or in the case of newsletter subscription they can unsubscribe. Consents were stored in the project repository.

For physical events, attendees were occasionally requested to sign attendance sheets or similar documents. This includes a column asking participants their consent preferences in relation to the publication and use of their image.

2. Data storage

Information related to participants was stored on the project's repository to enable the long-term storage and access to data by consortium members. Information was stored according to each event organised in the project. Information was stored as it is received by the project team.

All files sent to the repository comply with the locations, names and permissions as defined in the D6.1 - Data Management Plan.

3. Data quality assurance

The task leader/s was/were responsible for verifying that all required information is provided by participants, that it is stored and that instructions in the informed consents are enforced.

4. Utility and re-use

The dataset generated were used by consortium members to increase participants' engagement in the project. It also served to generate statistics and reports about the participants, which was aggregated or anonymized data that will not compromise personal details of the participants nor any other confidential information.

This information was not re-used outside of the project.

5. Data sharing

Data sharing is not applicable for this dataset. The EC might be informed of the number of participants that provided consent/ non-consent in official reports.

6. Archiving and preservation

The CATALISI consortium will retain generated data until five years after the balance of the project is paid or longer if there are ongoing procedures (such as audits, investigations or litigation). In this case, the data will be kept until they end.

WEBINARS AND OTHER VIDEO RECORDINGS DATASETS

The project organised and run webinars that were recorded for dissemination purposes and managed a project website and social media channels to raise awareness about the project, engage stakeholders, and disseminate information and results.

1. Data capture

Webinars and other activities were recorded with video in the following cases:

- Participants have been informed and able to withdraw consent to be recorded for the purpose of the webinar/ activity.
- Recording was necessary to fulfil the objectives of the project.
- Recording is in the public interest or is in the interests of the recorder, unless those interests are overridden by the interests of the participants that require protection of personal data.

If one of the above mentioned cases is applicable, all participants of the webinar or activity that were to be recorded were informed at the start that such recording will take place. The following information was disclosed to the participants:

- Confirmation the webinar/ activity will be recorded.
- Justification of the reason for the recording.
- Request consent for the recording: individuals who do not consent to the recording could still participate in the webinar/ activity. They were able to do this by turning off their camera and hiding/removing their name from the recording session so they can remain anonymous.

In the process of recording, the following was considered:

- If at any time there was a need to protect sensitive data, the recording was paused/ stopped.
- Any part of the recording that contains sensitive data was erased.
- Recordings with sensitive data were marked as such (if the case).

2. Data storage

Webinars and other video recordings were stored on the project's repository and/or public platforms (incl. on the project website).

All files sent to the repository comply with the locations, names and permissions as defined in the D6.1 - Data Management Plan.

3. Data quality assurance

The task leader/s was/were responsible for verifying the appropriateness of the convention applied and the organisation within the repository. Any recording uploaded to a public platform was also verified by another consortium member to confirm an adequate characterisation of the recording.

4. Utility and re-use

Webinars and other video recordings were used by the consortium members for dissemination purposes or to increase external engagement in the project.

5. Data sharing

Webinars and other video recordings were shared and made publicly available through the project website and/or a public platform.

6. Archiving and preservation

For files stored in the repository, the CATALISI consortium will retain generated data until five years after the balance of the project is paid or longer if there are ongoing procedures (such as audits, investigations or litigation). In this case, the data will be kept until they end.

For files stored in public platforms the project has no control in archiving and preservation.

PROJECT WEBSITE AND SOCIAL MEDIA DATASETS

The project partners run and managed a project website and social media platforms to raise awareness about the project, engage stakeholders, and disseminate information and results. Anonymous statistical information about the visitors to the website and users' engagement with social media was being collected.

1. Data capture

The project website was set up to provide statistics that were collected using a web analytics service. Only anonymised data was collected that can not be tracked back to a specific individual. Social media platforms include their own analytics services that were used to collect and provide information about user engagement on these platforms.

2. Data storage

In order to allow for a more thorough and varied analysis, data will remain stored on the analytics platforms. When relevant, data was exported to the project's documentation repository to enable access by consortium members. Data is stored separately, divided into the website and relevant social media platforms.

3. Data quality assurance

Data exported to the project's documentation repository was stored using a common naming convention to ensure easy access by consortium members. Whenever feasible, data was exported regularly (e.g. monthly) and consistently in terms of indicators. The task leader verified that the dataset is exported regularly and that it is consistent in terms of indicators.

4. Utility and re-use

The dataset generated was used by consortium members to analyse visitors and users' engagement with the project via the website and social media, and to adjust the existing strategy to improve engagement. The dataset was also used to generate statistics and reports about visitors and users, which was aggregated or anonymized data that is not compromising personal details of the participants nor any other confidential information. This information was and will not be re-used outside of the project.

5. Data sharing

Data sharing is not applicable for this dataset. Information extracted from the dataset was and will be made available via official reports.

6. Archiving and preservation

The CATALISI consortium will retain generated data until five years after the end of the project.

EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION WITH THIRD PARTIES DATASETS

The project partners engaged and communicated with third parties throughout the project on some of the planned activities.

1. Data capture

Communication and Information exchange between the partners and third parties was carried out through different platforms that included e-mail, the F6S platform, or other communication platforms.

2. Data storage

The communications and information exchanged were primarily stored on the platforms used for this purpose. Specific information and documentation that is relevant to all partners was occasionally exported and saved on the project repository to enable access by

consortium members. Information was stored separately according to the type of activity that the communication is related to. Such information was exported as soon as it was available.

3. Data quality assurance

Information and documentation of interest that was exported to the project's documentation repository was stored using a common naming convention to ensure easy access by consortium members. The task leader/s verified that the information and documentation is consistent in terms of its naming and organisation within the repository.

4. Utility and re-use

The dataset was used primarily to enable access to information and documentation by consortium members involved in activities. With exemption to the third parties involved, no other third parties were using the information and documentation contained in the data set.

5. Data sharing

Data sharing is not applicable for this dataset.

6. Archiving and preservation

The CATALISI consortium will retain generated data until five years after the end of the project.

APPENDIX 4 – COLLABORATION AGREEMENT BETWEEN CATALISI, AUPAEU AND ACCELERATE_FUTUREHEI

COLLABORATION AGREEMENT

Between

**CATALISI – Catalysation of institutional transformations of Higher Education Institutions
through the adoption of acceleration services**

AND

Accelerate_FutureHEI - Entrepreneurial & Innovative Universities Acceleration Programme

AND

aUPaEU - A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities

AND

**APRE – Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea, UIIN – University Industry
Innovation Network B.V. and Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya**

This Collaboration Agreement ('the Agreement') is made and effective on date of signature,

BETWEEN:

The CATALISI project, funded by the HORIZON EUROPE of the European Commission under Grant Agreement n° 101094917, represented by the APRE Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea, as the project coordinator, located at Via Cavour 71 – 00184 Rome – Italy, represented for the purposes of signing this Agreement by Chiara Pocaterra, Head of Projects Department APRE

AND:

The Accelerate_FutureHEI supported by funded by the HORIZON EUROPE of the European Commission under Grant Agreement n° 101095083 represented by UIIN, as the project coordinator, located at Science Park 402, 1098XH Amsterdam, The Netherlands, represented for the purposes of signing this Agreement by Arno Meerman, CEO & Founder at UIIN.

AND:

The aUPaEU, supported by the HORIZON EUROPE of the European Commission under Grant Agreement n° 101095314, represented by Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, as the project coordinator, located at Carrer Jordi Girona 31, Barcelona 08034, Spain, represented for the purposes of signing this Agreement by Prof. Jesus Angel Alcober Segura, delegate of the rector for the Unitel Digital Campus and Associate Professor of the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya.

RECITALS

The CATALISI project is dedicated to support HEIs in successfully implementing strategies and individualized pathways for institutional transformation through the adoption of innovative acceleration services. The CATALISI model focuses on three main domains for institutional transformation: Research Careers and Talent Support, Open Science and Public Engagement and Sustainable Research and Education. These domains encompass various intervention areas and are integrated with seven targeted and innovative acceleration services designed to facilitate and catalyse institutional transformations in R&I. These services include: Living Labs, Design Lab for Transformational Pathways: strategy and agenda setting, Counselling, Reinforcement of Human Capital: capacity building & outreach, Predictive Study on Skills Anticipation, Marketplace and Community of Practice (CoP).

The Accelerate_FutureHEI project supports Higher Education Institutions in advancing institutional transformation toward more entrepreneurial and innovative futures. It provides a structured methodology and practical tools to develop and implement Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects (ITAPs), tailored to the needs and context of each HEI. The project framework focuses on four transformation domains: Entrepreneurial Skills and Mindset of Students, Impactful Research and Research Valorisation, Institutional Support for Engagement and Innovation, and Strategic Partnerships for Stronger Engagement. These thematic areas are supported by a suite of acceleration services including personalised coaching, thematic workshops, peer-to-peer exchange, training programmes, investment planning, and expert-guided roadmap development. Together, these services aim to enhance

the capacity of HEIs to integrate innovation, societal engagement, and entrepreneurship into their core missions.

The **aUPaEU project** aims at accelerating the transformation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) by developing *Agora*, a digital platform inspired by the Greek concept of a shared public space. This platform enables all stakeholders to access and offer acceleration services while contributing their expertise. aUPaEU supports the institutional transformation of HEIs by focusing on six key areas: capacity, infrastructure, and resource sharing; researcher career attractiveness; collaboration with research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem actors; open science; societal outreach; and gender equality. Through this integrated approach, the project empowers HEIs, university networks, and alliances to achieve long-term, sustainable R&I transformations.

NOW, THEREFORE, in consideration of the above RECITALS and the mutual promises and conditions contained in this Agreement, the Parties agree as follows:

TERMS AND DURATION

This Agreement shall be effective commencing at the date of the signature of this contract and will be in force until the end of the respective projects. All activities conducted before this date within the vision of the joint collaboration will be deemed to fall under this Agreement.

The collaboration among the projects will be extended, if requested by one or all representatives of the projects, by written notice.

This Collaboration Agreement is a non-binding expression of mutual interest and shall not create any legally enforceable rights or obligations between the parties. Any references to terms such as 'Agreement', 'obligations', 'breach'; or 'jurisdiction' are used solely for structural clarity and shall not be interpreted as creating enforceable duties.

It also does not imply any financial commitment between the parties. Any costs related to joint activities shall be borne individually by the respective parties unless otherwise agreed in writing.

OBJECTIVES

The objective of this Agreement is to express the willingness of the parties to engage in joint effort to:

1. JOINT DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION, IN PARTICULAR:

- Promotion via the projects social networks. These actions are envisaged to increase the outreach of the projects' respective accounts: following each other on social media, sharing each other's posts related to the project if the content is suitable to the respective target audiences, creating specific joint contents to be published in the respective accounts and tagging each other in special posts.
- Exchange of non-confidential information on the success stories based on the achievements/outcomes of the projects.
- Promote and organize joint events: Collaboration in internal events. When deemed necessary, the other party will be invited to participate in workshops, roundtables, info days, and related activities.
- Common organization of Communication and Dissemination events. Each project will decide on a case-by-case basis if they are interested in organizing/attending those events. This can include common dissemination materials or participation in relevant trade-fairs, conferences, trainings, workshops, seminars, etc.

2. JOINT RESULTS

- Development of 2 joint Policy Briefs including policy recommendations for policy-makers and decision-makers.
- Joint participation at international conferences, such as the INORMS Congress 2025 in Madrid.
- Synergy and collaboration among the three parties on the acceleration services developed, through their inclusion in the Agoras platforms created by the aUPaEU project.

3. OTHER

N/A

Other specific activities under this Agreement will be identified through consultation between the two parties.

CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION AND PERSONAL DATA

For the purposes of this Agreement, by Confidential Information is meant any data or information that is proprietary to or possessed by the Parties, the Consortium partners, and the Consortium as a whole, and not generally known to the public or that has not yet been revealed, whether in tangible or intangible form, whenever and however disclosed, including, but not limited to:

- a) any scientific or technical information, invention, design, process, procedure, formula, improvement, technology or method;
- b) any concepts, samples, reports, data, know-how, works-in-progress, designs, drawings, photographs, development tools, specifications, software programs, source code, object code, flow charts, and databases;
- c) any marketing strategies, plans, financial information, or projections, operations, sales estimates, business plans and performance results, past, present or future business activities, or those of its affiliates, subsidiaries and affiliated companies;
- d) trade secrets; plans for products or services, and customer or supplier lists;
- e) any other information that should reasonably be recognized as Confidential Information by the Parties and/or the Consortium.

The Parties agree not to disclose or communicate the above-mentioned information, in any manner, either during the Agreement or after the termination of the Agreement. The Parties understand that any breach of this provision, or that of any other Confidentiality and Non-Disclosure Agreement, is a material breach of this Agreement.

The parties agree to treat shared information with discretion and mutual respect. This clause does not impose any legal obligations but reflects the spirit of trust within this cooperation.

To the extent the parties feel the need to disclose confidential information, they may do so only after obtaining written authorization from the Consortium.

Any personal data included in this Agreement must be processed in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on

the protection of natural persons with regard to the Processing of Personal Data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). Such data must be processed by the data controller solely for the purposes of the implementation, management and monitoring of this Agreement. This does not affect its possible transmission to bodies entrusted with monitoring or inspection tasks in application of Union law.

TERMINATION

Each Party may terminate the Agreement at any time by giving written notice to the other Party, sent by email with acknowledgement of receipt. Such termination notice shall run from the end of the calendar month during which the notice of termination was received, unless otherwise agreed upon by the Parties.

Either Party may terminate the Agreement immediately if the other Party has committed a material breach of the Agreement and, where such breach is capable of remedy, has failed to remedy that breach within thirty (30) days of receipt of written notice from the first Party specifying the breach and requiring it to be remedied.

Such termination shall not prejudice any other remedy to which the terminating party may be entitled, wither by law, in equity, or under this Agreement.

Expiration or termination of the Agreement shall not release or discharge either Party from any obligation, debt or liability which shall have previously existed, and remain to be performed upon the date of expiration or termination.

NOTICES

Any notice or communications to be given hereunder by any party to the other may be affected either by Personal delivery in writing, or by mail. Each party may change their address by written notice in accordance with this paragraph.

On behalf of: APRE – Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea (Italy)

Name and Surname: Chiara Pocaterra

Title: Head of Projects Department

Email: pocaterra@apre.it

On behalf of: UIIN - University Industry Innovation Network (The Netherlands)

Name and Surname: Arno Meerman

Title: CEO & Founder

Email: meerman@uiin.org

On behalf of: Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya

Name and Surname: Jesus Angel Alcober Segura

Title: Delegate of the rector for the Unite! Digital Campus and Associate Professor

Email: jesus.alcober@upc.edu

This Agreement shall not be subject to any jurisdiction or interpreted under any specific national law, as it is not intended to be legally binding.

On behalf of Party: APRE Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea (Italy)

On behalf of the project: CATALISI

Name: Chiara Pocaterra

Job Title: Head of Projects Department

Signature:
03/09/2025

On behalf of Party: UIIN – University Industry Innovation Network B.V.

On behalf of the project: Accelerate_FutureHEI

Name: Arno Meerman

Job Title: Founder & CEO at UIIN

Signature:
10/09/2025

On behalf of Party: Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya

On behalf of the project: aUPaEU

Name: Prof. Jesus Angel Alcober Segura

Job Title: Project Manager, Coordinator of
aUPaEU project

Signature:
03/07/2025

APPENDIX 5 – ‘AGORA’ PLATFORM USERS AGREEMENT

“AGORA” Platform Users Agreement

This agreement (hereinafter referred to as “Agreement”), is entered by and between:

1. **UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE CATALUNYA (“UPC”)**, having its registered office or based in CARRER JORDI GIRONA 31, BARCELONA 08034, Spain, VAT number: ESQ0818003F,

(in representation of the aUPaEU Consortium Members)

AND

2. **AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA (APRE)**, having its registered office based in Via Cavour, 71, 00184, ROME, ITALY. VAT Number: 03929151003.

(in representation of the CATALISI Consortium members)

(hereinafter individually referred to as the “User” or “the Users”).

(Hereinafter, individually or jointly, “the Parties” or “the Entities”)

Hereto mutually recognize their sufficient legal capacity to commit their respective institutions and

WHEREAS

- I. The European project “*A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities*” (aUPaEU) funded by the European Research Executive Agency (REA) under grant agreement number 101095314, is based on the collaboration of five academic institutions of two European partnerships in the framework of the European University Initiative, EPICUR and UNiTE!: Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT), Institut Polytechnique de Grenoble (INP GRENOBLE), Politecnico di Torino (POLITO) and Uniwersytet im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu (AMU) (hereinafter, “the aUPaEU Consortium Members”).
- II. Within the scope of the aUPaEU project, the aUPaEU Consortium Members have worked together to integrate and implement acceleration services in the context of a coordinated support system for higher education institutions (HEIs), networks, university alliances and their umbrella organizations. In the framework of this collaboration, the AGORA platform has been created (hereinafter, “AGORA” or “the Platform”).
- III. Following the Greek concept of the agora, the creation of the platform under this name becomes a shared space where all stakeholders can provide and consume accelerated services while contributing their knowledge and expertise. The Platform is based on the open-source Odoo software, which is licensed under [LGPLv3](#), and its customization has been developed by the aUPaEU Consortium Members.
- IV. The User APRE is a no-profit research association (counting more than 160 members) based in Italy and born in 1989 with the mission to support and promote Italian participation in the European Union Research and Innovation (R&I) programmes, by providing information, training and assistance services. APRE Projects Department directly participates in the Horizon Europe calls through its vertical and transversal expertise. APRE is the coordinator of the CATALISI project. For this reason, the User has expressed its interest in accessing and using the Platform for research, education and

innovation purposes in accordance with the terms and conditions set out in this Agreement and on the Platform.

- V. UPC as coordinator in the aUPaEU project is authorized to act on behalf of and represent the aUPaEU Consortium Members in accordance with the aUPaEU Consortium Agreement (clause 6.4.4 as drafted by Addendum I to the aUPaEU Consortium Agreement) to sign this Agreement with the User.

Therefore, the Parties agree to subscribe this Agreement, which will be governed by the following

CLAUSES

FIRST - Object of the Agreement

The purpose of this Agreement is to set out the terms and conditions under which the User may use the Platform.

SECOND - Principles for the use of the Platform

2.1. The Platform will draw on resources (hereinafter "Resources") from:

- public sources which allow it,
- generated by the aUPaEU Consortium Members or within the framework of their European partnerships, provided they are authorized to share it,
- uploaded by the users of the Platform,
- sent by users and/or third parties in order to make it known within the Platform.

The above Resources shall not contain personal data, unless there is a legitimate basis for its publication or sharing with third parties. The processing of personal data shall only be lawful if any of the conditions set out in Article 6 of the GDPR are met.

2.2. The Platform will comply with all applicable legal aspects. Therefore, Users will be informed of all those requirements that need to be fulfilled.

2.3. In order to optimize the performance of the Platform, the Resources included in the Platform may be subject to artificial intelligence (AI) systems. Any implementation of AI systems will follow the principles of the European Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act). We will disclose any use of AI in our online terms and conditions and provide more information about how we use AI responsibly and ethically.

2.4. The use of the Platform by the Users is exclusively for research, education and innovation purposes, unless otherwise stated in writing by the aUPaEU Consortium Members or UPC, on their behalf.

2.5. Users are responsible for their use of the Platform, as well as for having the necessary authorizations to share Resources and/or data.

2.6. The members of the aUPaEU Consortium will not be responsible for the use made of the Resources provided, nor for the Resources shared by Users

2.7. The authorization to use AGORA does not imply the licensing of the patent, the trademark or copyrights or any other property right of the aUPaEU Consortium Members which, if it was the case, would need to be the object of a specific agreement.

2.8. During the aUPaEU project, use of the Platform will be free of charge for the Users.

THIRD - Commitments of the Users

The User authorized to access the Platform undertake to:

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- Make appropriate use of the Platform.
- To use the Resources provided only for research, education and innovation purposes, under no circumstances for commercial purposes.
- To communicate to the person indicated in clause ELEVENTH, the persons authorized to provide Resources by the User.
- To provide truthful information when requested to do so in the framework of the use of the Platform.
- To inform the aUPaEU Consortium Members about any error or improvement they detect.
- To inform employees or other authorized persons linked to the User who have access to the Platform of the obligations contained in this Agreement.
- Not to claim any ownership rights or rights of prior use over the platform or the Resources contained therein.
- Comply with all other obligations established in this Agreement, as well as the latest terms and conditions set out in the Platform.

FOURTH - Confidential Information

In general terms, Resources shall not contain information of a confidential nature. The Parties shall avoid sharing Confidential Information (refers to the confidential information supplied through the AGORA by either Party –or third party- for the duration of the right of use, such as texts, designs, diagrams, drawings, photographs, recordings or models or any other that is clearly identified as confidential by its owner) and shall only share it when it is essential and necessary for the specific purpose. The aUPaEU Consortium Members shall not be liable for any unauthorized disclosure, misappropriation or misuse of Confidential Information.

The Users who become aware of any unauthorized disclosure, misappropriation or misuse of Confidential Information shall bring it to the attention of the owner or the aUPaEU Consortium Members.

The User agrees that during and after the termination of this Agreement it will not use the Confidential Information to which it has had access within the Platform and will not disclose it without the prior written consent by the party owning such information.

FIFTH - Duration

This Agreement shall enter into force on the date of the last signature and shall remain in force until the end of the aUPaEU project (date 31 December 2027), unless the User specifies another date. This period is the time during which the User has the right to access and use the Platform.

At the end of the aUPaEU project, the aUPaEU Consortium Members will analyze the use made by all users and will assess the continuity of the Platform. In this regard, the aUPaEU Consortium Members will inform the users of the decision reached and the new conditions for its use, as well as the terms of reuse of the Resources, if necessary. In the event that the User would like to continue using the Platform, a new agreement must be formalized with the new conditions.

In the event that the Platform service is not continued to be provided by the aUPaEU Consortium Members, users may reuse the catalogues of Resources developed in the Platform under the terms of the license applicable to such resources and only for research, education and innovation purposes.

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SIXTH - Consideration

The use of the Platform will be free of charge for the duration of the aUPaEU project funded by the European Research Executive Agency.

SEVENTH - Termination of the Agreement

The following may be grounds for terminating this Agreement:

- a) The term of the Agreement ending.
- b) The Parties' mutual agreement in writing.
- c) One of the Parties wishing to terminate the Agreement, for which a written statement must be made three months in advance.
- d) Failure by one of the Parties to fulfil its obligations in the thirty days following notification in writing by the other party, which can in this case unilaterally terminate the agreement.
- e) A judicial decision that declares this Agreement null and void.
- f) The causes outlined in this Agreement and those set out in current legislation.

Without prejudice to the will of the Parties to carry out their commitments under this Agreement, this Agreement may be terminated at any time by either Party if either of the Parties fails to fulfil its obligations under this Agreement despite having been requested to do so in writing.

Any use outside of the purposes as stated in point 2.4, authorizes the aUPaEU Consortium Members to terminate access to AGORA. The aUPaEU Consortium Members reserve the right to take the appropriate measures, allowed by law, in the event of inappropriate use of AGORA by User which could result in any damage to the legitimate interests of the aUPaEU Consortium Members.

In the event of breach of this Agreement, the Parties expressly acknowledge and accept the right of both to request specific compliance with the obligations agreed here, together with any other measures they deem appropriate to compensate for the damage caused as a result of such breach.

Upon termination of this Agreement, access to the Platform will be automatically removed. In the event that within the Platform has been made available to the User a space for storing documentation owned by the User, the User will be left a reasonable time to retrieve it and determine the fate of the Resources(keep or delete). As for the Resources provided within the Platform by the User and/or added by the aUPaEU Consortium Members to carry out the functions of the Platform, it will be accessible to all other users as long as it is not obsolete or until the Platform is enabled for use. The termination of the Agreement does not exempt the Parties from compliance with confidentiality agreed upon in clause FOURTH of this Agreement.

EIGHTH - Liability and warranties

The User understands that the Resources provided by AGORA is not the responsibility of aUPaEU Consortium Members.

The Resources and services related to the Platform are provided on an "as is" basis. The aUPaEU Consortium Members make no representations or warranties of any kind, either express or implied, with respect to the Resources or related services, such as, but not limited to, any

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representation or warranty as to the accuracy, completeness, availability, accessibility, fitness for a particular purpose, or that use of the Resources will not infringe any rights of any third party. The aUPaEU Consortium Members shall not be liable for any liability or damages with respect to any claim by the User or any third party arising out of or in connection with this Agreement or the use of the Resources or services provided within the Platform.

NINTH - Protection of Personal Data

The parties declare to comply with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 (hereinafter, "GDPR") and any other applicable data protection regulations.

Each party will process the personal data of the representatives and interlocutors of the other party as a data controller within the meaning of Article 4.7 of the GDPR. The purpose of the processing will be to formalize and manage this Agreement and to carry out the actions arising from it, in order to comply with the legal relationship formalized by means of this Agreement. For the execution of the rights recognized in the GDPR (access to data, rectification, deletion, portability, opposition and requesting the limitation of processing) the interested parties may contact the other party at the references and addresses listed in the heading of this document.

The fulfilment of the purposes of this Agreement does not require one party to process personal data of third parties on behalf of or for the account of the other party, so it is not necessary to formalize an agreement for processing within the meaning of Article 28 of the GDPR.

The personal data of the user's of the Platform will be processed in accordance with the data protection information provided at the time of accessing the Platform or indicated in the Platform's privacy policy.

TENTH - Miscellaneous

10.1. This Agreement does not presuppose or imply property rights over AGORA Platform or the Resources contained therein.

10.2. Neither Party may assign, in whole or in part, the rights and obligations of this Agreement to any third party, except with the express written consent of the other party.

10.3. Nothing in this Agreement shall be construed to place either Party in a relationship of employment, partnership, or joint venture. No Party shall have the right or power to oblige or bind any other Party in any manner. Each party must fulfil its commitments under its sole responsibility, with its own means and in accordance with the established in this Agreement.

10.4. Any amendment or addition to this Agreement shall require the signature of the Parties' authorized legal representatives in order to be valid.

10.5. Neither Party shall be liable to the other Party for failure or delay in performing its obligations hereunder if such failure or delay is due to circumstances beyond its reasonable control including, without limitation, acts of any governmental body, endemic, epidemic, pandemic, war, insurrection, sabotage, embargo, fire, flood, strike or other labour disturbance, interruption of or delay in transportation, unavailability of or interruption or delay in telecommunications (including cyberattacks) or third party services, or failure of third party software.

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10.6. The execution of this Agreement to access and use the Platform is non-exclusive and shall not preclude either Party from entering into similar agreements with other institutions.

ELEVENTH - Notices

Each Party shall designate a person to carry out those actions necessary to implement the provisions of this Agreement. These persons shall have the following functions, without prejudice to any other functions assigned to them:

- To address problems that may arise regarding the interpretation or application of this Agreement;
- To follow up the implementation of this Agreement and to ensure that measures are taken in accordance with this Agreement;
- In the event of the Agreement's termination, to propose its continuation or the manner and deadline for completing the actions already under way;
- To establish and organize the proceedings that are the object of this Agreement.

The designated persons and their contact details shall be as follows:

- For UPC (in representation of the aUPaEU Consortium Members): Jesus Alcober, aUPaEU project coordinator, e-mail: agora@widening.eu
- For APRE (in representation of the CATALISI Consortium members): Laura Mentini, CATALISI Project coordinator, e-mail: mentini@agre.it

In the event that one of the Parties wants to modify the person designated in this clause, it shall notify the other Party in writing.

TWELVETH - Litigation and applicable regulations

The Parties undertake to resolve amicably any disagreement arising from the development or interpretation of this Agreement.

This Agreement shall be construed in accordance with and governed by the laws of Belgium excluding its conflict of law provisions. Sole competent courts will be the courts of Brussels.

AS WITNESS

The Parties have caused this Agreement to be duly signed by the undersigned authorized representatives.

The electronic signature of this Agreement has the same legal effect, validity and enforceability as a handwritten signature. An electronic signature is accepted if it is made through a recognized certification service provider. The maintenance of records in electronic format will have the same validity as a documentary file in paper format.

UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE CATALUNYA

Signature

Prof. Francesc Torres Torres
Rector

AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA

Signature(s)

APRE

Agenzia per la Promozione
della Ricerca Europea

Via Cavour 71 - 00184 Roma

Tel. +39.0648939903 - Fax +39.06.48902550
segreteria@apre.it - <http://www.apre.it>

Name(s): Chiara Pocaterra

Title(s): Head of Projects Department – APRE

Date: 07/10/2025